

Complete Integers

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Abstract

In this document we will see the complete integers (\mathbb{Z}_C): a superset of integer numbers (\mathbb{Z}), which also contains the dual of \mathbb{Z} along parity (dis-integers, \mathbb{Z}_D). Then we will see some properties of these numbers and of the even unit ($l \in \mathbb{Z}_D$).

Moreover we will define perenomials and hyper-perenomials, an extension of polynomials, which allow us to write functions defined by cases with a single formula.

Resumo

En ĉi tiu dokumento ni vidos la kompletajn entjerojn (\mathbb{Z}_C): superaro de entjeraj nombroj (\mathbb{Z}), kiu ankaŭ enhavas la dualon de \mathbb{Z} laŭ pareco (neentjerojn, \mathbb{Z}_D). Tiam ni vidos iujn ecojn de ĉi tiuj nombroj kaj de la para unuo ($l \in \mathbb{Z}_D$).

Cetere ni difinos la perenomojn kaj la hiperperenomojn, etendon de polinomoj, kiujn ni uzos por skribi funkciojn per kazoj kun ununura formulo.

Somari

In chest document i definirin i intîrs complets (\mathbb{Z}_C) che i numars intîrs (\mathbb{Z}) a son un lôr sotinsiemi, e che a tegnin dentri ancje il duâl di \mathbb{Z} cun rispîet a la paritât (disintîrs, \mathbb{Z}_D). Po daspò i viodarin diversis proprietâts di chescj numars e de unitât pâr ($l \in \mathbb{Z}_D$).

Cun di plui i definirin i perenomîs e i iper-perenomîs, une estension dai polinomîs, che o doprarin par scrivi funzions par câs dome cuntune formule.

Sommario

In questo documento vedremo gli interi completi (\mathbb{Z}_C): un sovrainsieme dei numeri interi (\mathbb{Z}), il quale contiene anche il duale di \mathbb{Z} rispetto alla parità (disinteri, \mathbb{Z}_D). In seguito vedremo alcune proprietà di questi numeri e dell'unità pari ($l \in \mathbb{Z}_D$).

Inoltre definiremo perenomi, ed iper-perenomi: un'estensione dei polinomi che ci permetterà di scrivere funzioni per casi usando un'unica formula.

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Nomenclature

Costants

o Odd zero, *see Remark 1.7, page 15.*

l Even unit, *see Definition 1.11, page 14.*

Variables

n (Complete) natural number.

x Real number.

z (Complete) integer number.

z Complex number.

p Parity, *see Notation.*

v Value, *see Notation.*

\vec{v} Vector.

M Matrix.

Functions

$\text{par}(z)$ Parity function, *see Definition 1.4, page 5.*

$\text{val}(z)$ Value function, *see Definition 1.3, page 3.*

$\text{sgn}(x)$ Sign function, *see section 3.1, page 45.*

$\mathbf{1}(x)$ Heaviside step function, *see section 3.2, page 45.*

$\chi_A(x)$ Indicator function, *see section 3.5, page 50.*

$\Pi(x)$ Rect function, *see section 3.3, page 47.*

$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x)$ Selector function, *see section 3.4, page 48.*

Notation

$\begin{pmatrix} m_{1,1} & \dots & m_{1,m} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ m_{n,1} & \dots & m_{n,m} \end{pmatrix}$ Matrix.

$\begin{pmatrix} v_1 \\ \dots \\ v_n \end{pmatrix}$ Vector.

$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}$ Complete integer number, *see Definition 1.1, page 1.*

Operators

\oplus Sum modulo 2, *see page 1.*

z^* Complex conjugate.

\sqcup Partition, *see page 7.*

$*$ Convolution.

\circ Hadamard product, *see Theorem 2.9, page 34.*

$\hat{f} = \mathcal{F}[f]$ (Discrete) Fourier transform.

Number sets

\mathbb{C} Field of complex numbers.

\mathbb{I} Field of imaginary numbers.

\mathbb{R} Field of real numbers.

\mathbb{Q} Field of rational numbers.

\mathbb{Z} Ring of integer numbers.

\mathbb{N} Ring of natural numbers.

\mathbb{N}^+ Naturals without zero.

\mathbb{F}_2 Field of integers modulo 2, *see page 1.*

\mathbb{Z}_e Set of even numbers, *see page 5.*

- \mathbb{Z}_o Set of odd numbers, *see page 5*.
- \mathbb{Z}_D Set of dis-integers, *see Definition 1.6, page 7*.
- \mathbb{N}_D Set of dis-naturals, *see Definition 1.7, page 9*.
- \mathbb{Z}_{De} Set of dis-even integers, *see Definition 1.7, page 9*.
- \mathbb{Z}_{Do} Set of dis-odd integers, *see Definition 1.7, page 9*.
- \mathbb{Z}_C Ring of complete integers, *see Definition 1.1, page 1*.
- \mathbb{N}_C Ring of complete naturals, *see Definition 1.7, page 9*.
- \mathbb{Z}_{Ce} Ring of complete even integers, *see Definition 1.7, page 9*.
- \mathbb{Z}_{Co} Set of complete odd integers, *see Definition 1.7, page 9*.
- \mathbb{Q}_H Set of half-complete rationals, *see Definition 1.8, page 9*.

Chapter 1

Complete integer numbers

In this chapter we will define the ring of complete integers (\mathbb{Z}_C) and we will see that it is a superset of \mathbb{Z} . Then we will call the remaining dis-integers (\mathbb{Z}_D) which are the dual of integers (\mathbb{Z}) along parity (e.g. in \mathbb{Z} the unit is odd, in \mathbb{Z}_D the unit is even).

Definition 1.1 (Complete integers). Let's define the set of the complete integer numbers as

$$\mathbb{Z}_C := \mathbb{Z} \times \mathbb{F}_2 \tag{1.1}$$

$\mathbb{F}_2 = \mathbb{Z}/2\mathbb{Z} = \{0, 1\}$
[Lid+97]

We will represent a complete integer $z \in \mathbb{Z}_C$ in the form of a tuple $z = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}$, with v (value) $\in \mathbb{Z}$, p (parity) $\in \mathbb{F}_2$.

Definition 1.2 (Ring \mathbb{Z}_C). Let's define \mathbb{Z}_C as a commutative ring with unit:

Given $\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} a + c \\ b \oplus d \end{bmatrix} \tag{1.2}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot c \\ b \cdot d \end{bmatrix} \tag{1.3}$$

$$\begin{array}{c|cc} \oplus & 0 & 1 \\ \hline 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{array}$$

Proof. Now let's check if the given definition is valid:

1. Associative property of addition

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} \right) + \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a + c \\ b \oplus d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a + c + e \\ b \oplus d \oplus f \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \left(\begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c + e \\ d \oplus f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a + c + e \\ b \oplus d \oplus f \end{bmatrix}$$

2. Additive identity ($0 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$)

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + 0 = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a+0 \\ b \oplus 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix}$$

3. Additive inverse

$$-\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} -a \\ b \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} -a \\ b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a-a \\ b \oplus b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0$$

4. Commutative property of addition

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a+c \\ b \oplus d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c+a \\ d \oplus b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix}$$

5. Associative property of multiplication

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} \right) \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot c \\ b \cdot d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot c \cdot e \\ b \cdot d \cdot f \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c \cdot e \\ d \cdot f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot c \cdot e \\ b \cdot d \cdot f \end{bmatrix}$$

6. Commutative property of multiplication

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot c \\ b \cdot d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c \cdot a \\ d \cdot b \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix}$$

7. Multiplicative identity ($1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$)

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} 1 = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot 1 \\ b \cdot 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix}$$

8. Distributive property

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \left(\begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} \right) &= \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c+e \\ d \oplus f \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a(c+e) \\ b(d \oplus f) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} ac+ae \\ bd \oplus bf \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} ac \\ bd \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} ae \\ bf \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e \\ f \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 1.1 (Powers of \mathbb{Z}_C).

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}^n = \begin{bmatrix} v^n \\ p \end{bmatrix} \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^+$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}^0 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 1$$

Proof.

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}^n = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \cdots \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}}_n = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} v \cdots v \\ p \cdots p \end{bmatrix}}_n = \begin{bmatrix} v^n \\ p^n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v^n \\ p \end{bmatrix}$$

The first from definition of power, the second for Equation 1.3, the last because $1^n = 1$, $0^n = 0$. Instead for $n = 0$ we have $v^0 = 1$ and $0^0 = 1$ [Knu92]. □

1.1 Value and parity

In this section we will see two functions, that explain the role of v and p , and see their properties.

Definition 1.3 (Value function).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val}: \mathbb{Z} \cup \mathbb{Z}_C &\rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \\ \text{val}(z) &:= z \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z} \\ \text{val} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \right) &:= v \end{aligned} \tag{1.4}$$

Theorem 1.1 (Properties of value). *Given $x, y \in \mathbb{Z} \vee x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_C$ and $z \in \mathbb{Z}$*

1. *Value is odd.*

$$\text{val}(-x) = -\text{val}(x) \tag{1.5}$$

2. *Linearity.*

$$\text{val}(x + y) = \text{val}(x) + \text{val}(y) \tag{1.6}$$

$$\text{val}(z \cdot x) = z \text{val}(x) \tag{1.7}$$

3. *Idempotence of the value.*

$$\text{val} \circ \text{val} = \text{val} \tag{1.8}$$

4. *Completely multiplicative.*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val}(1) &= 1 \\ \text{val}(x \cdot y) &= \text{val}(x) \cdot \text{val}(y) \end{aligned} \quad (1.9)$$

Proof.

1.

$$\begin{aligned} x \in \mathbb{Z} &\Rightarrow -x \in \mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow \text{val}(-x) = -x = -\text{val}(x) \\ x = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C &\Rightarrow \text{val}(-x) = \text{val}\left(-\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}\right) = \text{val}\left(\begin{bmatrix} -v \\ p \end{bmatrix}\right) = -v = -\text{val}(x) \end{aligned}$$

2. a) $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val}(x) &= x; \text{val}(y) = y \\ \text{val}(x + y) &= x + y = \text{val}(x) + \text{val}(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{b) } x = \begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix}, y = \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val}(x) + \text{val}(y) &= v_x + v_y \\ \text{val}(x + y) &= \text{val}\left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix}\right) = \text{val}\left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x + v_y \\ p_x \oplus p_y \end{bmatrix}\right) = v_x + v_y \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{And then } \text{val}(nx) = \text{val}(\underbrace{x + \cdots + x}_n) = \underbrace{\text{val}(x) + \cdots + \text{val}(x)}_n = n \text{val}(x)$$

for $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

$$\text{Finally } \text{val}(zx) = \begin{cases} z \text{val}(x) & z \in \mathbb{N} \\ -\text{val}(-zx) = z \text{val}(x) & z \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \mathbb{N} \end{cases}$$

3.

$$\text{val}(x) \in \mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow \text{val}(\text{val}(x)) = \text{val}(x)$$

4. a) $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val}(x) &= x; \text{val}(y) = y \\ \text{val}(x \cdot y) &= x \cdot y = \text{val}(x) \cdot \text{val}(y) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{b) } x = \begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix}, y = \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{val}(x) \cdot \text{val}(y) &= v_x \cdot v_y \\ \text{val}(x \cdot y) &= \text{val}\left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix}\right) = \text{val}\left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x \cdot v_y \\ p_x \cdot p_y \end{bmatrix}\right) = v_x \cdot v_y \end{aligned}$$

□

Definition 1.4 (Parity function).

$$\text{par}: \mathbb{Z} \cup \mathbb{Z}_C \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_2$$

$$\text{par}(z) := \begin{cases} 0 & z \in \mathbb{Z}_e \\ 1 & z \in \mathbb{Z}_o \end{cases} \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (1.10)$$

$$\text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \right) := p$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{Z}_e &= 2\mathbb{Z} = \{2z: z \in \mathbb{Z}\} \\ \mathbb{Z}_o &= 2\mathbb{Z} + 1 = \\ &= \{2z + 1: z \in \mathbb{Z}\} \end{aligned}$$

Remark 1.1. Observe that $\text{par}|_{\mathbb{Z}}(z) = \chi_{\mathbb{Z}_o}(z)$.

Theorem 1.2 (Properties of parity). *Given $x, y \in \mathbb{Z} \vee x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_C$ and $z \in \mathbb{Z}$*

1. *Parity is even.*

$$\text{par}(-x) = \text{par}(x) \quad (1.11)$$

2. *Linearity.*

Since $\text{par}(x) \in \mathbb{F}_2$ the sum operator must be replaced by exclusive or (\oplus) and so the homogeneity property is valid modulus 2.

$$\text{par}(x + y) = \text{par}(x) \oplus \text{par}(y) \quad (1.12)$$

$$\text{par}(z \cdot x) \equiv_2 z \text{par}(x) \quad (1.13)$$

3. *Idempotence of the parity.*

$$\text{par} \circ \text{par} = \text{par} \quad (1.14)$$

4. *Completely multiplicative.*

$$\begin{aligned} \text{par}(1) &= 1 \\ \text{par}(x \cdot y) &= \text{par}(x) \cdot \text{par}(y) \end{aligned} \quad (1.15)$$

Proof.

1. a) $x \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\text{par}(-x) = \begin{cases} 0 & -x \in \mathbb{Z}_e \\ 1 & -x \in \mathbb{Z}_o \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 0 & x \in \mathbb{Z}_e \\ 1 & x \in \mathbb{Z}_o \end{cases} = \text{par}(x)$$

b) $x = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$

$$\text{par}(-x) = \text{par} \left(- \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \right) = \text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} -v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \right) = p = \text{par}(x)$$

2. a) $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}$

x	y	$\text{par}(x)$	$\text{par}(y)$	$\text{par}(x) \oplus \text{par}(y)$	$x + y$	$\text{par}(x + y)$
\mathbb{Z}_e	\mathbb{Z}_e	0	0	0	\mathbb{Z}_e	0
\mathbb{Z}_e	\mathbb{Z}_o	0	1	1	\mathbb{Z}_o	1
\mathbb{Z}_o	\mathbb{Z}_e	1	0	1	\mathbb{Z}_o	1
\mathbb{Z}_o	\mathbb{Z}_o	1	1	0	\mathbb{Z}_e	0

b) $x = \begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix}, y = \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$

$$\text{par}(x + y) = \text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} \right) = \text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x + v_y \\ p_x \oplus p_y \end{bmatrix} \right) = p_x \oplus p_y$$

$$\text{par}(x) \oplus \text{par}(p_y) = p_x \oplus p_y$$

And then for $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\text{par}(nx) = \text{par}(\underbrace{x + \cdots + x}_n) = \underbrace{\text{par}(x) \oplus \cdots \oplus \text{par}(x)}_n \equiv_2 n \text{par}(x)$$

$$\text{Finally } \text{par}(zx) \begin{cases} \equiv_2 z \text{par}(x) & z \in \mathbb{N} \\ = \text{par}(-zx) \equiv_2 -z \text{par}(x) \equiv_2 z \text{par}(x) & z \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \mathbb{N} \end{cases}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{par}(x) \in \mathbb{F}_2 \subset \mathbb{Z} \Rightarrow \text{par}(\text{par}(x)) &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{par}(x) \in \mathbb{Z}_e \\ 1 & \text{par}(x) \in \mathbb{Z}_o \end{cases} = \\ &= \begin{cases} 0 & \text{par}(x) = 0 \\ 1 & \text{par}(x) = 1 \end{cases} = \text{par}(x) \end{aligned}$$

4. a) $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}$

x	y	$\text{par}(x)$	$\text{par}(y)$	$\text{par}(x) \cdot \text{par}(y)$	$x \cdot y$	$\text{par}(x \cdot y)$
\mathbb{Z}_e	\mathbb{Z}_e	0	0	0	\mathbb{Z}_e	0
\mathbb{Z}_e	\mathbb{Z}_o	0	1	0	\mathbb{Z}_e	0
\mathbb{Z}_o	\mathbb{Z}_e	1	0	0	\mathbb{Z}_e	0
\mathbb{Z}_o	\mathbb{Z}_o	1	1	1	\mathbb{Z}_o	1

b) $x = \begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix}, y = \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$

$$\text{par}(x) \cdot \text{par}(y) = p_x \cdot p_y$$

$$\text{par}(x \cdot y) = \text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x \\ p_x \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v_y \\ p_y \end{bmatrix} \right) = \text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_x \cdot v_y \\ p_x \cdot p_y \end{bmatrix} \right) = p_x \cdot p_y$$

□

Lemma 1.2 (Parity of powers).

$$\text{par}(z^n) = \text{par}(z) \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^+$$

Proof. From 1.15 and since $0^n = 0$ and $1^n = 1$

$$\text{par}(z^n) = [\text{par}(z)]^n = \text{par}(z)$$

□

1.2 Related sets

Now we will see some subsets of \mathbb{Z}_C which will be useful later.

Definition 1.5 (Integers prime). Let's define the set of the integers prime as

$$\mathbb{Z}' := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C : p = \text{par}(v) \right\} \quad (1.16)$$

Definition 1.6 (Dis-integers). Let's define the set of the dis-integers as

$$\mathbb{Z}_D := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C : p \neq \text{par}(v) \right\} \quad (1.17)$$

Remark 1.2. $\{\mathbb{Z}', \mathbb{Z}_D\}$ is a partition of \mathbb{Z}_C .

$$\mathbb{Z}' \sqcup \mathbb{Z}_D = \mathbb{Z}_C$$

$$A \sqcup B = C \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} A \cup B = C \\ A \cap B = \emptyset \end{cases}$$

Theorem 1.3 (\mathbb{Z} and \mathbb{Z}' are isomorphic). *The function $f_{\mathbb{Z}} : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}'$ defined as*

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}(z) = \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \text{par}(z) \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.18)$$

is a isomorphism.

Proof. Let's check if $f_{\mathbb{Z}}$ is a homomorphism:

$$a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$$

- For addition:

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}(a + b) = \begin{bmatrix} a + b \\ \text{par}(a + b) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a + b \\ \text{par}(a) \oplus \text{par}(b) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}(a) + f_{\mathbb{Z}}(b) = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ \text{par}(a) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} b \\ \text{par}(b) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a + b \\ \text{par}(a) \oplus \text{par}(b) \end{bmatrix}$$

- For multiplication:

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}(a \cdot b) = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot b \\ \text{par}(a \cdot b) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot b \\ \text{par}(a) \cdot \text{par}(b) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}(a)f_{\mathbb{Z}}(b) = \begin{bmatrix} a \\ \text{par}(a) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} b \\ \text{par}(b) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot b \\ \text{par}(a) \cdot \text{par}(b) \end{bmatrix}$$

- For multiplicative identity:

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}(1) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 1$$

Now let's check if $f_{\mathbb{Z}}$ is an isomorphism, that is if $\exists f_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}: \mathbb{Z}' \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ homomorphism.

Picking $z \in \mathbb{Z}'$ we can write $z = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix}$ with $v = \text{val}(z) \in \mathbb{Z}$, so let's define $g: \mathbb{Z}' \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$

$$g\left(\begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix}\right) := v$$

Now let's prove that $g(z) = f_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}(z)$, in other words $f_{\mathbb{Z}} \circ g = \text{id}$:

$$f_{\mathbb{Z}}\left(g\left(\begin{bmatrix} z \\ \text{par}(z) \end{bmatrix}\right)\right) = f_{\mathbb{Z}}(z) = \begin{bmatrix} z \\ \text{par}(z) \end{bmatrix}$$

and $g^{-1}(z) = f_{\mathbb{Z}}(z)$, or $g \circ f_{\mathbb{Z}} = \text{id}$:

$$g(f_{\mathbb{Z}}(z)) = g\left(\begin{bmatrix} z \\ \text{par}(z) \end{bmatrix}\right) = z$$

□

Since \mathbb{Z}' is isomorphic to \mathbb{Z} , and so the two cannot be distinguished [Art91], we won't write \mathbb{Z}' anymore and we will use the notation $\begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix}$ to denote elements in \mathbb{Z} too.

More precisely we will write, with an abuse of notation, $\mathbb{Z}' = \mathbb{Z}$ and $\begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix} = v$ meaning respectively $\mathbb{Z}' = f_{\mathbb{Z}}(\mathbb{Z})$ and $\begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix} = f_{\mathbb{Z}}(v)$.

Remark 1.3. Note that, by definition,

$$\text{val}(z) = \text{val}(f_{\mathbb{Z}}(z)); \quad \text{par}(z) = \text{par}(f_{\mathbb{Z}}(z))$$

Remark 1.4 (\mathbb{Z}_D is not a ring). It's easy to see that \mathbb{Z}_D is not closed under addition:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Definition 1.7. We can define the restrictions of \mathbb{Z}_D and \mathbb{Z}_C to natural numbers:

$$\mathbb{N}_D := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_D : v \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \quad (1.19)$$

$$\mathbb{N}_C := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C : v \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \quad (1.20)$$

We can also extend the sets of even and odd numbers:

$$\mathbb{Z}_{D_e} := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_D \right\} = \{z \in \mathbb{Z}_D : \text{par}(z) = 0\} \quad (1.21)$$

$$\mathbb{Z}_{D_o} := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_D \right\} = \{z \in \mathbb{Z}_D : \text{par}(z) = 1\} \quad (1.22)$$

$$\mathbb{Z}_{C_e} := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C \right\} = \{z \in \mathbb{Z}_C : \text{par}(z) = 0\} = \mathbb{Z}_e \sqcup \mathbb{Z}_{D_e} \quad (1.23)$$

$$\mathbb{Z}_{C_o} := \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C \right\} = \{z \in \mathbb{Z}_C : \text{par}(z) = 1\} = \mathbb{Z}_o \sqcup \mathbb{Z}_{D_o} \quad (1.24)$$

Definition 1.8 (Half-complete rational numbers). We now define the set of half-complete rational numbers as

$$\mathbb{Q}_H := \mathbb{Q} \times \mathbb{F}_2 = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} : v \in \mathbb{Q}, p \in \mathbb{F}_2 \right\} \quad (1.25)$$

And we extend val and par in such a way

$$\text{val} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \right) = v \quad \forall \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H \quad (1.26)$$

$$\text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \right) = p \quad \forall \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H \quad (1.27)$$

Remark 1.5.

$$\mathbb{Z} \sqcup \mathbb{Z}_D = \mathbb{Z}_C \subset \mathbb{Q}_H$$

Definition 1.9 (Ring \mathbb{Q}_H). Let's define \mathbb{Q}_H as a commutative ring with unit which extends \mathbb{Z}_C :

Given $\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} a + c \\ b \oplus d \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.28)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c \\ d \end{bmatrix} := \begin{bmatrix} a \cdot c \\ b \cdot d \end{bmatrix} \quad (1.29)$$

Theorem 1.4 (Division of complete integers). *The division between a complete integer $\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$ and a complete odd $\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o} \setminus \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\}$ is an half-complete rational:*

$$\frac{\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1/v_2 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H$$

Besides, $\mathbb{Q}_H = \left\{ \frac{x}{y} : x \in \mathbb{Z}_C, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o} \setminus \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \right\}$.

Proof. Let's start checking $\frac{\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1/v_2 \\ p \end{bmatrix}$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}} \begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1/v_2 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{v_1}{v_2} v_2 \\ p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix}$$

Now let's check that $\begin{bmatrix} v_1/v_2 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H$:

$$\frac{v_1}{v_2} \in \mathbb{Q} \text{ since } v_1, v_2 \in \mathbb{Z} \text{ and } p \in \mathbb{F}_2$$

Finally we are going to prove that all \mathbb{Q}_H can be generated in such way:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H \implies v \in \mathbb{Q} \implies v = \frac{a}{b} : a, b \in \mathbb{Z} \implies \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} a \\ p \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} b \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}}$$

□

Corollary 1.4.1. *The division between an half-complete rational $\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H$ and a complete odd $\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o} \setminus \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\}$ is an half-complete rational:*

$$\frac{\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} v_1/v_2 \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Q}_H$$

The proof is similar to the one above.

Definition 1.10 (Complete rational numbers). Defining

$$\mathbb{Q}_{\overline{\mathbb{H}}} := \left\{ \frac{q}{\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} : q \in \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{H}} \right\} \quad (1.30)$$

we can define the set of complete rational numbers as

$$\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}} := \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{H}} \sqcup \mathbb{Q}_{\overline{\mathbb{H}}} \quad (1.31)$$

Theorem 1.5 (Complete division of complete integers). *The division between two complete integers $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}}$, $\text{val}(y) \neq 0$ is a complete rational and $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}} = \left\{ \frac{x}{y} : x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}}, \text{val}(y) \neq 0 \right\}$.*

Proof. If $y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}_o}$ then for Theorem 1.4 we know $\frac{x}{y} \in \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{H}} \subset \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}}$ and that $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{H}} = \left\{ \frac{x}{y} : x \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}}, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}_o} \setminus \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \right\}$.

Otherwise, if $y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}_e}$ then $\exists z \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}_o}$ such that $y = z \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$ ($z = \begin{bmatrix} \text{val}(y) \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$). Now for Theorem 1.4 $q = \frac{x}{z} \in \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{H}}$ and so $\frac{x}{y} = \frac{x}{z \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} = \frac{q}{\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} \in \mathbb{Q}_{\overline{\mathbb{H}}} \subset \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}}$.

Then

$$\mathbb{Q}_{\overline{\mathbb{H}}} = \left\{ \frac{q}{\begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} : q \in \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{H}} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{x}{z \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} : x \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}}, z \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}_o} \setminus \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \right\} = \left\{ \frac{x}{y} : x \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}}, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}_e} \setminus \{0\} \right\}$$

And finally

$$\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}} = \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{H}} \cup \mathbb{Q}_{\overline{\mathbb{H}}} = \left\{ \frac{x}{y} : x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}}, \text{val}(y) \neq 0 \right\}$$

□

Lemma 1.3. *We can now see that \mathbb{Q} is a subset of $\mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}}$:*

$$\mathbb{Q} \subset \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}}$$

Proof. Each element of \mathbb{Q} is a ratio between two integers:

$$\forall q \in \mathbb{Q} \exists x, y \in \mathbb{Z}, y \neq 0: q = \frac{x}{y}$$

but then $q = \frac{x}{y} \in \mathbb{Q}_{\mathbb{C}}$ because $x, y \in \mathbb{Z} \subset \mathbb{Z}_{\mathbb{C}}$ and $\text{val}(y) \neq 0$. □

1.3 Ratio between even numbers

Lemma 1.4 (Parity of the ratio between even numbers). *The ratio between two even numbers could be either odd or even.*

Proof. If $\frac{x}{y} = z$ we know that $x = yz$, but since y is even x will be always even, independently of the parity of z .

Another way to see this is:

$$z = \frac{x}{y} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} \text{val}(x) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} \text{val}(y) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{val}(x) \\ \frac{\text{val}(x)}{\text{val}(y)} \\ 0/0 \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\text{val}(z) = \frac{\text{val}(x)}{\text{val}(y)}$ and $\text{par}(z) = \frac{0}{0}$ which could be either 0 or 1. \square

Now that we know the ratio between even numbers could be either even or odd, we expect that such ratio has two results. The two results will have the same value but one will be even and the other odd; such change of parity could be done adding an odd zero $\left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}\right)$:

Theorem 1.6 (Ratio between even numbers).

$$\frac{a}{b} = \text{val}\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) \vee \text{val}\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \forall a, b \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}$$

Example 1.1.

$$\text{val}\left(\frac{2}{2}\right) = 1$$

$$\frac{2}{2} = 1 \vee 1 + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 1 \vee \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

In facts $2 \cdot 1 = 2$ and $2 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 2$.

Example 1.2.

$$\text{val}\left(\frac{4}{6}\right) = \frac{2}{3} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} 3 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}} = \begin{bmatrix} 2/3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{4}{6} = \frac{2}{3} \vee \frac{2}{3} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{2}{3} \vee \begin{bmatrix} 2/3 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

In facts $6 \cdot \frac{2}{3} = 4$ and $6 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 2/3 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 4$.

Figure 1.1: $1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}; \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}; \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}; 5 = \begin{bmatrix} 5 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}; \begin{bmatrix} 7 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 5 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$

Figure 1.2: $x = 1; x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}; x = 3 \cdot 1; x = 3 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$

1.4 Cartesian plot of half-complete rationals

We can see the sum between half-complete rationals as a vector sum on a bi-dimensional cartesian plane with the value on x-axis and parity on y-axis (Figure 1.1).

Obviously \mathbb{Q}_H is not a vector space because \mathbb{Q} and \mathbb{F}_2 are different fields. In fact on x-axis we could have only rational numbers and on y-axis we have only 0 and 1 cyclically repeated.

The previous representation is valid also for "scalar product", which is the product by an integer (Figure 1.2).

Remark 1.6. Repeating parity on the negative side of the y-axis we notice that the "vectors" which goes up by one or goes down by one alongside y-axis are indeed the same (Figure 1.3). So we don't need to repeat parity (Figure 1.4).

Figure 1.4: $3 + 3 = 2 \cdot 3 = 6$; $3 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 6 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$

1.5 Even unit

Definition 1.11 (Even unit).

$$l := \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

In this section we will analyse the even unit l and its properties.

First of all let's say why we call it even unit: its parity is $\text{par}(l) = 0$ and so it's in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e} ; then its value is $\text{val}(l) = 1$, and in fact we can see it is the unit of the \mathbb{Z}_{C_e} ring:

$$l \cdot \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \forall \begin{bmatrix} v \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}$$

Lemma 1.5 (Powers of l).

$$l^n = l \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^+$$

Proof. For Lemma 1.1

$$l^n = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^n = \begin{bmatrix} 1^n \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = l$$

□

Lemma 1.6 (Roots of l).

$$\sqrt[n]{l} = l \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}^+$$

Proof.

$$\sqrt[n]{l} = \sqrt[n]{l^n} = l$$

□

Remark 1.7 (Odd zero).

$$\mathfrak{o} := 1 - l = l - 1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

is the odd zero because $\text{par}(1 - l) = 1$ and $\text{val}(1 - l) = 0$.

Theorem 1.7 (Expression of complete integer). *Given* $\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_C$

$$k := p \oplus \text{par}(v)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} = v + k(l - 1)$$

Remark 1.8. k is a very important value for a complete integer number: if it is 0 it means the number is an integer, otherwise if it is 1 the number is a dis-integer.

Proof.

$$1. \ z \in \mathbb{Z} \implies k = 0$$

$$v + k(l - 1) = v = z$$

$$2. \ z \in \mathbb{Z}_D \implies k = 1$$

$$v + k(l - 1) = v + (l - 1) = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \oplus 1 \end{bmatrix} = z$$

□

Example 1.3. Given $\begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$ we know $k = 1 \oplus \text{par}(2) = 1$, and so

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = 2 + 1(l - 1) = 1 + l$$

And in fact $1 + l = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$.

Remark 1.9. The parity of the norm of a complete integer¹ is equal to k :

$$k = \text{par} \left(\left\| \begin{pmatrix} v \\ p \end{pmatrix} \right\| \right)$$

Proof. For 1.2 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{par} \left(\left\| \begin{pmatrix} v \\ p \end{pmatrix} \right\| \right) &= \text{par} \left(\left\| \begin{pmatrix} v \\ p \end{pmatrix} \right\|^2 \right) = \text{par}(v^2 + p^2) = \\ &= \text{par}(v^2) \oplus \text{par}(p^2) = \text{par}(v) \oplus \text{par}(p) = \text{par}(v) \oplus p = k \end{aligned}$$

□

1.5.1 Approximations of l

Definition 1.12. Given $N \in \mathbb{N}$: $N \geq n \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$l^- := \frac{2N}{2N+1} \tag{1.32}$$

$$l^+ := \frac{2N}{2N-1} \tag{1.33}$$

Lemma 1.7. l^- and l^+ are good approximations of l

Proof. First let's see that they are both in \mathbb{Q} and in \mathbb{Q}_H since $2N \in \mathbb{N} \subset \mathbb{Z}_C$ and $2N \pm 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_o \subset \mathbb{Z}_{C_o} \setminus \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\}$.

Then we will check the parity (using Theorem 1.4):

$$\text{par}(l^\pm) = \text{par}(2N) = 0 = \text{par}(l)$$

Finally let's check the value. We know that N is a very big natural, by definition, so we can think its value is near ∞ , and so:

$$\text{val}(l^\pm) \approx \text{val} \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{2n}{2n \mp 1} \right) = \text{val}(1) = \text{val}(l)$$

And so we can say $l^\pm \approx l$. □

Lemma 1.8.

$$x^{l^\pm} \approx |x| \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}$$

The result makes sense because being $\text{val}(l^\pm) \approx 1$ we expect a result similar to $x^1 = x$, but we know also that l^\pm have an even parity and so we expect the result being non negative, as for all even powers.

¹As said before $\mathbb{Q}_H = \mathbb{Q} \times \mathbb{F}_2$ ($\mathbb{Z}_C \subset \mathbb{Q}_H$) is not a vector space, but we can think of it like a peculiar vector space.

Proof. Knowing that x^{2N} cannot be negative we can write $x^{2N} = |x|^{2N}$, and so

$$x^{l^\pm} = x^{\frac{2N}{2N \mp 1}} = \sqrt[2N \mp 1]{x^{2N}} = \sqrt[2N \mp 1]{|x|^{2N}} = |x|^{\frac{2N}{2N \mp 1}} \approx |x|^1$$

Another way to prove this is to use complex roots [Jef05]:

- We know that $\sqrt[2N \mp 1]{x^{2N}}$ has $2N \mp 1$ complex roots of module $|x|^{\frac{2N}{2N \mp 1}} \approx |x|$, and being $2N \mp 1$ odd one root will always be real. Moreover, since x^{2N} cannot be negative, $\sqrt[2N \mp 1]{x^{2N}}$ must be non negative.
- We know that $\sqrt[2N \mp 1]{x}$ has $2N \mp 1$ complex roots, and being $2N \mp 1$ odd one root will always be real. Then $\sqrt[2N \mp 1]{x^{2N}}$ will be always non negative with module $|x|^{\frac{2N}{2N \mp 1}} \approx |x|$.

□

1.6 Exponential of complete integers

In Lemma 1.8 we saw that $x^{l^\pm} \approx |x|$, and in Lemma 1.7 we saw that $l^\pm \approx l$, thus it's seems reasonable to define $x^l := |x| \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{R}$. To do this we define a family of exponential rings over \mathbb{Z}_C and prove it is a good definition:

Definition 1.13 (Exponential rings over \mathbb{Z}_C). $\forall x \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$

$$E_x : \mathbb{Z}_C \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ \begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \mapsto x^{v-k} |x|^k$$

and finally $x^z := E_x(z) \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_C$.

$$k = p \oplus \text{par}(v)$$

Remark 1.10.

$$x^l = E_x(l) = |x|$$

as we wanted.

Remark 1.11. These are not real exponential rings because each E_x must have been a homomorphism between the additive group of \mathbb{Z}_C and its multiplicative group [Dri84], but instead it is a homomorphism between the additive group of \mathbb{Z}_C and the multiplicative group of \mathbb{R} . Anyway this definition is good for our purposes.

Proof. Firstly we have to prove that each E_x is an exponential ring:

1.

$$E_x \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p_1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ p_2 \end{bmatrix} \right) = E_x \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_1 + v_2 \\ p_1 \oplus p_2 \end{bmatrix} \right) = x^{v_1+v_2-k_{12}} |x|^{k_{12}}$$

$$k_{12} = (p_1 \oplus p_2) \oplus \text{par}(v_1 + v_2) = p_1 \oplus p_2 \oplus \text{par}(v_1) \oplus \text{par}(v_2) = k_1 \oplus k_2$$

$$E_x \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p_1 \end{bmatrix} \right) E_x \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ p_2 \end{bmatrix} \right) = x^{v_1-k_1} |x|^{k_1} x^{v_2-k_2} |x|^{k_2} = x^{v_1+v_2-k_1-k_2} |x|^{k_1+k_2}$$

And since in \mathbb{F}_2 $k_1 + k_2 = k_1 \oplus k_2 + 2k_1k_2 = k_{12} + 2k_1k_2$

k_1	k_2	$k_1 \oplus k_2$	k_1k_2	$k_1 + k_2$	$k_1 \oplus k_2 + 2k_1k_2$
0	0	0	0	0	0
0	1	1	0	1	1
1	0	1	0	1	1
1	1	0	1	2	2

$$E_x \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p_1 \end{bmatrix} \right) E_x \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ p_2 \end{bmatrix} \right) = x^{v_1+v_2-k_{12}-2k_1k_2} |x|^{k_{12}+2k_1k_2} =$$

$$= E_x \left(\begin{bmatrix} v_1 \\ p_1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v_2 \\ p_2 \end{bmatrix} \right) \left(\frac{|x|}{x} \right)^{2k_1k_2}$$

But we know that $\left(\frac{|x|}{x} \right)^{2k_1k_2} = (\pm 1)^{2k_1k_2} = 1$.

2. $E_x(0) = x^0 |x|^0 = 1$

Then we must check that $E_x(z) = x^z \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}$, since $\mathbb{Z} \subset \mathbb{Z}_C$. If $z \in \mathbb{Z}$ we know that $k = 0$ (Remark 1.8), and so:

$$E_x(z) = x^{v-k} |x|^k = x^v = x^z$$

□

Definition 1.14 (Exponential ring for zero).

$$E_0(z) := 0^{\text{val}(z)} = \begin{cases} 0 \\ 1 \end{cases} \quad \text{val}(z) = 0 \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_C$$

This definition could be proved to be correct from the proof of the previous definition.

1.6.1 Calculus

In this subsection we will analyse the function

$$f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$x \mapsto x^{a+bl} ; \text{ with } a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$$

Derivative

$$f'(x) = \frac{d}{dx} x^{a+bl} = (a + bl)x^{(a-1)+bl} = (a + b)x^{a-1+bl}$$

We applied the derivative rule for polynomials. The last passage is correct because in \mathbb{R} (codomain) it makes no sense to talk about parity, so the coefficient $a + bl$ can be substituted by its value $a + b$. This substitution cannot be done at the exponent because it lives in \mathbb{Z}_C , where parity is a fundamental property.

Lemma 1.9.

$$\frac{d}{dx} x^z = \text{val}(z)x^{z-1} \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_C$$

Proof.

$$\frac{d}{dx} x^z = \frac{d}{dx} x^{v-k}|x|^k = \frac{dx^{v-k}}{dx}|x|^k + x^{v-k} \frac{d|x|^k}{dx} = (v-k) \underbrace{x^{v-k-1}|x|^k}_{x^{z-1}} + x^{v-k} \frac{d|x|^k}{dx}$$

- $k = 0$

$$(v-0)x^{z-1} + x^{v-0} \underbrace{\frac{d|x|^0}{dx}}_0 = vx^{z-1} = \text{val}(z)x^{z-1}$$

- $k = 1$

$$(v-1)x^{z-1} + x^{v-1} \underbrace{\frac{d|x|^1}{dx}}_{\text{sgn}(x) = \frac{|x|}{x} = x^{l-1}} =$$

$$= (v-1)x^{z-1} + x^{v-1+l-1} = (v-1)x^{z-1} + \underbrace{x^{v-k-1}|x|^k}_{x^{z-1}} = \text{val}(z)x^{z-1}$$

□

Antiderivative

$$F(x) = \int x^{a+bl} dx = \frac{x^{(a+1)+bl}}{(a+1)+bl} + c = \frac{x^{a+1+bl}}{a+b+1} + c \quad \text{with } c \in \mathbb{R}$$

Like for derivative.

Lemma 1.10.

$$\int x^z dx = \frac{x^{z+1}}{\text{val}(z)+1} + c \quad \text{with } c \in \mathbb{R}; \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_C$$

Proof.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \frac{x^{z+1}}{\text{val}(z)+1} + c = \text{val}(z+1) \frac{x^z}{\text{val}(z)+1} = \cancel{\text{val}(z)+1} \frac{x^z}{\cancel{\text{val}(z)+1}}$$

□

Chapter 2

Perenomials

In this chapter we will extend polynomials in order to have also dis-integers exponents.

Definition 2.1 (Polynomial ring). Let's call P the set of polynomials over field K [Hal72]:

$$P := K[x] = \{p(x) = \sum_0^n p_i x^i : n \in \mathbb{N}, \vec{p} \in K^{n+1}\}$$

Definition 2.2 (Dis-polynomials). Now we will define the dis-polynomials as:

$$P_D := \{q(x) = \sum_0^m q_i x^{i+\sigma} : m \in \mathbb{N}, \vec{q} \in K^{m+1}\}$$

Lemma 2.1 (Relationship beetwen polynomials and dis-polynomials).

$$q(x) \in P_D \implies \exists s(x) \in P : q(x) = s(x)x^\sigma \quad (2.1)$$

$$p(x) \in P \implies \exists t(x) \in P_D : p(x) = t(x)x^\sigma \quad (2.2)$$

Proof. 1. Given

$$q(x) = \sum_0^m q_i x^{i+\sigma}$$

we can define

$$s(x) := \sum_0^m q_i x^i \in P$$

and so

$$s(x)x^\sigma = \sum_0^m q_i x^i x^\sigma = \sum_0^m q_i x^{i+\sigma} = q(x)$$

2. We can define

$$t(x) := p(x)x^\sigma \in P_{\mathbb{D}}$$

and so

$$t(x)x^\sigma = p(x)x^{2\sigma} = p(x)x^{\emptyset} = p(x)$$

□

Definition 2.3 (Degree of a dis-polynomial). given $P_{\mathbb{D}} \ni q(x) = s(x)x^\sigma$

$$\deg(q) := \deg(s)$$

Lemma 2.2 (Polynomials and dis-polynomials).

$$P \cap P_{\mathbb{D}} = \{0\}$$

Proof.

$$p \in P \cap P_{\mathbb{D}} \Leftrightarrow p \in P \wedge p \in P_{\mathbb{D}}$$

$$p \in P \Leftrightarrow p(x) = \sum_0^n p_i x^i$$

$$q \in P_{\mathbb{D}} \Leftrightarrow q(x) = \sum_0^m q_i x^{i+\sigma}$$

$\exists (\vec{p}, \vec{q}), (n, m): p = q?$

$$\sum_0^n p_i x^i = \sum_0^m q_i x^{i+\sigma} \Leftrightarrow \sum_0^n p_i x^i - \sum_0^m \beta_i x^{i+\sigma} = 0 \quad \forall x$$

assuming $N = \max\{n, m\}$ and $p_i = q_j = 0 \quad \forall i = n+1, \dots, N; j = m+1, \dots, N$

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_0^N p_i x^i - q_i x^{i+\sigma} &= \sum_0^N p_i x^i - q_i x^i x^\sigma = \\ &= \sum_0^N (p_i - q_i x^\sigma) x^i = 0 \quad \forall x \Leftrightarrow \vec{p} = \vec{q} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

□

Definition 2.4 (Perenomials). We define the set of complete polynomials (or perenomials) as:

$$P_{\mathbb{C}} := \{r(x) = p(x) + q(x): p \in P, q \in P_{\mathbb{D}}\}$$

Theorem 2.1 (Polynomials, dis-polynomials and perenomials).

1. $P \subset P_C$
2. $P_D \subset P_C$
3. $P \cup P_D \subsetneq P_C$

Proof. From Lemma 2.2 we know that $0 \in P \cap P_D$

1. $p(x) = p(x) + 0 \wedge 0 \in P_D \implies p \in P_C \quad \forall p \in P$
2. $q(x) = 0 + q(x) \wedge 0 \in P \implies q \in P_C \quad \forall q \in P_D$
3. From previous points we see that $P \cup P_D \subset P_C$, moreover

$$\exists t(x) = 1 + x^\sigma \in P_C; t \notin P \cup P_D$$

□

2.1 Parity of perenomials

Theorem 2.2 (Even–odd decomposition of a perenomial). *Given $r(x) = p(x) + s(x)x^\sigma$, calling $f_e(x) = \frac{f(x)+f(-x)}{2}$ the even part of f and $f_o(x) = \frac{f(x)-f(-x)}{2}$ the odd part of f [IEE02]:*

1. $r_e(x) = p_e(x) + s_o(x)x^\sigma$
2. $r_o(x) = p_o(x) + s_e(x)x^\sigma$

Proof.

1.

$$\begin{aligned} r_e(x) &= \frac{r(x) + r(-x)}{2} = \frac{p(x) + s(x)x^\sigma + p(-x) + s(-x)(-x)^\sigma}{2} = \\ &= \frac{[p(x) + p(-x)] + s(x)x^\sigma - s(-x)x^\sigma}{2} = \\ &= \frac{[p(x) + p(-x)] + [s(x) - s(-x)]x^\sigma}{2} = \\ &= \frac{p(x) + p(-x)}{2} + \frac{s(x) - s(-x)}{2}x^\sigma = p_e(x) + s_o(x)x^\sigma \end{aligned}$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned}
r_o(x) &= \frac{r(x) - r(-x)}{2} = \frac{p(x) + s(x)x^\circ - p(-x) - s(-x)(-x)^\circ}{2} = \\
&= \frac{[p(x) - p(-x)] + s(x)x^\circ + s(-x)x^\circ}{2} = \\
&= \frac{[p(x) - p(-x)] + [s(x) + s(-x)]x^\circ}{2} = \\
&= \frac{p(x) - p(-x)}{2} + \frac{s(x) + s(-x)}{2}x^\circ = p_o(x) + s_e(x)x^\circ
\end{aligned}$$

□

Definition 2.5 (Even-nomials). Let's define the set of even-nomials as:

$$P_e := \{v(x) : v \in P_C; v \text{ even}\}$$

v is even if $v(x) = v_e(x)$ or, in an equivalent way, $v(x) = v(-x)$.

Definition 2.6 (Odd-nomials). Let's define the set of odd-nomials as:

$$P_o := \{w(x) : w \in P_C; w \text{ odd}\}$$

w is odd if $w(x) = w_o(x)$ or, in an equivalent way, $w(x) = -w(-x)$.

Lemma 2.3 (Even- and odd-nomials).

$$P_e \cap P_o = \{0\}$$

Proof.

$$t(x) \in P_e \cap P_o \Leftrightarrow t(-x) = -t(-x) \Leftrightarrow t(-x) = 0$$

□

Theorem 2.3 (Even-, odd- and perenomials).

1. $P_e \subset P_C$
2. $P_o \subset P_C$
3. $P_e \cup P_o \subsetneq P_C$

Proof.

1. By definition.

2. By definition.

3. From previous points we see that $P_e \cup P_o \subset P_C$, moreover

$$\exists t(x) = 1 + x^\sigma \in P_C$$

$$t_e(x) = 1; t_o(x) = x^\sigma \implies t \neq t_e \wedge t \neq t_o \implies t \notin P_e \cup P_o$$

□

Lemma 2.4 (Perenomial decomposition by parity).

$$r \in P_C \Leftrightarrow r(x) = v(x) + w(x); \quad v \in P_e, w \in P_o$$

Proof.

\implies

$$r(x) = r_e(x) + r_o(x)$$

\Leftarrow by definition.

□

Definition 2.7 (Perenomial units). let's define:

- $x^0 = 1$ as *perenomial even unit*.
- x^σ as *perenomial odd unit*.

Remark 2.1 (Unit). $\forall r \in P_C$

1. $|r(x)x^0| = |r(x)|$
2. $|r(x)x^\sigma| = |r(x)|$

Proof.

1. $|r(x)x^0| = |r(x) \cdot 1| = |r(x)|$
2. $|r(x)x^\sigma| = |r(x)||x^\sigma| = |r(x)|$

□

Remark 2.2 (Parity of the units).

1. $x^0 \in P_e$
2. $x^\sigma \in P_o$

Lemma 2.5 (Relationship between even- and odd-nomials).

$$w(x) \in P_o \implies \exists t(x) \in P_e : w(x) = t(x)x^\sigma \quad (2.3)$$

$$v(x) \in P_e \implies \exists t(x) \in P_o : v(x) = t(x)x^\sigma \quad (2.4)$$

Proof.

1. Given

$$w(x) = p(x) + s(x)x^\sigma$$

$$w \in P_o \implies w(x) = w_o(x) = p_o(x) + s_e(x)x^\sigma$$

defining

$$t(x) := s_e(x) + p_o(x)x^\sigma$$

$$t(-x) = s_e(-x) + p_o(-x)(-x)^\sigma = s_e(x) - p_o(x)(-x^\sigma) = t(x) \implies t \in P_e$$

and so

$$t(x)x^\sigma = s_e(x)x^\sigma + p_o(x)x^{2\sigma} = w(x)$$

2. Defining

$$t(x) := v(x)x^\sigma \in P_o$$

so

$$t(x)x^\sigma = v(x)x^{2\sigma} = v(x)$$

□

Theorem 2.4 (Expression of even-nomials).

$$v(x) \in P_e \Leftrightarrow v(x) = \sum_0^n v_i x^{2i}; \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \vec{v} \in K^{n+1}$$

Proof.

\implies

$$\begin{aligned} v(x) &= v_e(x) = p_e(x) + s_o(x)x^\sigma = \\ &= \frac{\sum_0^n p_i [x^i + (-x)^i] + \sum_0^m s_i [x^i - (-x)^i] x^\sigma}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$x^i + (-x)^i = \begin{cases} 2x^i & i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e} \\ 0 & i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o} \end{cases}$$

we can say

$$\sum_0^n p_i [x^i + (-x)^i] = 2 \sum_0^n_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}} p_i x^i = 2 \sum_0^n_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}} p_i x^{il}$$

Since

$$x^i - (-x)^i = \begin{cases} 0 & x \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e} \\ 2x^i & i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o} \end{cases}$$

we can write

$$\sum_0^m s_i [x^i - (-x)^i] x^\sigma = 2 \sum_0^m_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}} s_i x^i x^\sigma = 2 \sum_0^m_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}} s_i x^{i+\sigma}$$

and from

$$\text{par}(i + \sigma) = \text{par}(i) \oplus 1 = 0$$

so

$$i + \sigma = (i + \sigma)l = il + 0 = il$$

and so

$$2 \sum_0^m_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}} s_i x^{i+\sigma} = 2 \sum_0^m_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}} s_i x^{il}$$

Defining

$$v_i := \begin{cases} p_i & i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}, i \leq n \\ s_i & i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}, i \leq m \\ 0 & \end{cases}$$

$$N := \max\{n, m\}$$

we can write

$$2 \sum_0^n_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}} p_i x^{il} = 2 \sum_0^N_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}} v_i x^{il}; \quad 2 \sum_0^m_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}} s_i x^{il} = 2 \sum_0^N_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}} v_i x^{il}$$

Finally

$$\begin{aligned} v(x) &= \frac{\sum_0^n p_i [x^i + (-x)^i] + \sum_0^m s_i [x^i - (-x)^i] x^{l-1}}{2} = \\ &= \frac{2 \sum_0^N_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_e}} v_i x^{il} + 2 \sum_0^N_{i \in \mathbb{Z}_{C_o}} v_i x^{il}}{2} = \sum_0^N v_i x^{il} \end{aligned}$$

\Leftarrow

$$v(-x) = \sum_0^n v_i(-x)^{il} = \sum_0^n v_i((-x)^l)^i = \sum_0^n v_i(x^l)^i = \sum_0^n v_i x^{il} = v(x)$$

□

Theorem 2.5 (Expression of odd-nomials).

$$w(x) \in P_o \Leftrightarrow w(x) = \sum_0^n w_i x^{il+\sigma}; \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \vec{w} \in K^{n+1}$$

Proof.

$$\exists t(x) \in P_e: w(x) = t(x)x^\sigma$$

$$t(x) \in P_e \Leftrightarrow t(x) = \sum_0^n w_i x^{il}$$

$$w(x) = \sum_0^n w_i x^{il} x^\sigma = \sum_0^n w_i x^{il+\sigma}$$

□

Lemma 2.6 (Sum of even-nomials).

$$v_1, v_2 \in P_e \implies v_1 + v_2 \in P_e$$

Proof.

$$(v_1 + v_2)(-x) = v_1(-x) + v_2(-x) = v_1(x) + v_2(x) = (v_1 + v_2)(x)$$

□

Lemma 2.7 (Sum of odd-nomials).

$$w_1, w_2 \in P_o \implies w_1 + w_2 \in P_o$$

Proof.

$$(w_1 + w_2)(-x) = w_1(-x) + w_2(-x) = (-w_1(x)) + (-w_2(x)) = -(w_1 + w_2)(x)$$

□

Lemma 2.8 (Product of even- and odd-nomials).

$$1. \ v_1, v_2 \in P_e \implies v_1 v_2 \in P_e$$

$$2. w_1, w_2 \in P_o \implies w_1 w_2 \in P_e$$

$$3. v \in P_e, w \in P_o \implies vw \in P_o$$

Proof.

$$1. v_1 v_2(-x) = v_1(-x)v_2(-x) = v_1(x)v_2(x) = v_1 v_2(x)$$

$$2. w_1 w_2(-x) = w_1(-x)w_2(-x) = (-w_1(x))(-w_2(x)) = w_1 w_2(x)$$

$$3. vw(-x) = v(-x)w(-x) = v(x)(-w(x)) = -vw(x)$$

□

Definition 2.8 (Degree of even- and odd-nomials).

$$t(x) = \sum_0^n t_i x^{il} \in P_e \quad \vee \quad \sum_0^n t_a x^{il+\sigma} \in P_o$$

So, analogously with polynomial, we will define:

$$\deg(t) := \min\{i: t_j = 0 \quad \forall j > i\}$$

Remark 2.3 (Degree of dis-polynomials). This definition can be used also for dis-polynomials, inasmuch it is coherent with Definition 2.3:

$$q \in P_D \implies \deg(q) = \deg(s): s \in P \wedge q(x) = s(x)x^\sigma$$

$$q(x) = s(x)x^\sigma = \sum_0^n s_i x^i x^\sigma = \sum_0^n s_i x^{i+\sigma}$$

$$\deg(q) = \deg(s) = \min\{i: s_j = 0 \quad \forall j > i\}$$

2.2 Perenomial matrix form

Lemma 2.9 (Perenomial coefficients matrix).

$$r \in P_C \Leftrightarrow \exists R: r(x) = \sum_0^N \sum_0^1 r_{i,j} x \begin{bmatrix} i \\ j \end{bmatrix}$$

Proof. For Lemma 2.4

$$P_C \ni r(x) = v(x) + w(x); v \in P_e, w \in P_o$$

$$v(x) = \sum_0^n v_i x \begin{bmatrix} i \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad w(x) = \sum_0^m w_i x \begin{bmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

assuming $v_i = w_j = 0 \quad \forall i = n+1, \dots, N; j = m+1, \dots, N$

$$R := \left(\begin{array}{c|c} | & | \\ \hline \vec{v} & \vec{w} \\ \hline | & | \end{array} \right) \quad \text{matrix } (N+1) \times 2$$

$$\sum_0^N \sum_j r_{i,j} x^{[j]} = \sum_0^N r_{i,0} x^{[0]} + r_{i,1} x^{[1]} = \sum_0^N v_i x^{[0]} + w_i x^{[1]} = v(x) + w(x)$$

□

Lemma 2.10 (R matrix from polynomial and dis-polynomial).

$$P_C \ni r(x) = p(x) + q(x)$$

$$p(x) = \sum_0^n p_i x^i \in P; \quad q(x) = \sum_0^m q_i x^{i+\sigma} \in P_D$$

so

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} p_0 & q_0 \\ q_1 & p_1 \\ p_2 & q_2 \\ q_3 & p_3 \\ \dots & \dots \end{pmatrix}$$

Proof.

$$p(x) = \sum_0^n p_i x^i = \sum_0^n p_i x^{[\text{par}(i)]}$$

$$q(x) = \sum_0^m q_i x^{i+\sigma} = \sum_0^m q_i x^{[1-\text{par}(i)]}$$

$$r(x) = \sum_0^N \sum_j r_{i,j} x^{[j]}$$

so

$$r_{i,\text{par}(i)} = p_i; \quad r_{i,1-\text{par}(i)} = q_i$$

□

Definition 2.9 (Perenomial degree).

$$r(x) = \sum_0^N \sum_j r_{i,j} x^{[j]}$$

$$\deg(r) := \min\{i: r_{k,0} = r_{k,1} = 0 \quad \forall k > i\}$$

Remark 2.4. This definition is coherent with previous ones for polynomials, dis-polynomials, even- and odd-nomials.

Remark 2.5.

$$r(x) = \sum_0^N \sum_j r_{i,j} x^{[j]} \implies \deg(r) \leq N$$

Theorem 2.6 (Perenomial matrix form).

$$r(x) = \sum_0^N \sum_j r_{i,j} x^{[j]}$$

$$\vec{x} := (1, x^l, x^2, \dots, x^{Nl}) = (x^{il} \forall i = 0, \dots, N)$$

$$\vec{u} := \begin{pmatrix} x^0 \\ x^\sigma \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ x^\sigma \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{vector of the perenomial units})$$

so

$$r(x) = \vec{x} R \vec{u}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{x} R \vec{u} &= \vec{x} \begin{pmatrix} | & | \\ \vec{v} & \vec{w} \\ | & | \end{pmatrix} \vec{u} = \vec{x} (\vec{v} + \vec{w} x^\sigma) = \sum_0^N x_i (v_i + w_i x^\sigma) = \sum_0^N x^{il} (v_i + w_i x^\sigma) = \\ &= \sum_0^N v_i x^{il} + w_i x^{il+\sigma} = \sum_0^N v_i x^{[0]} + w_i x^{[1]} \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 2.7 (Perenomial sum).

$$r(x) = r_1(x) + r_2(x) \Leftrightarrow R = R_1 + R_2$$

Proof.

$$r_1 = \vec{x} R_1 \vec{u}; \quad r_2 = \vec{x} R_2 \vec{u}$$

$$r = r_1 + r_2 = \vec{x} (R_1 + R_2) \vec{u}$$

□

Remark 2.6.

$$\deg(r) \leq \max\{\deg(r_1), \deg(r_2)\}$$

Proof.

R_1, R_2 matrices $(N + 1) \times 2$

We can always choose N : $N = \max\{\deg(r_1), \deg(r_2)\}$ since all next rows would be all zeros and so they would not change the result.

Therefore R is a $(N + 1) \times 2$ matrix, and for Remark 2.5 we have

$$\deg(r) \leq N = \max\{\deg(r_1), \deg(r_2)\}$$

□

Theorem 2.8 (Perenomial product).

$$r(x) = r_1(x)r_2(x) \Leftrightarrow R = R_1 * R_2$$

Proof.

$$r_1 = \vec{x}R_1\vec{u}, \quad r_2 = \vec{x}R_2\vec{u}; \quad R_1 : (n + 1) \times 2, \quad R_2 : (m + 1) \times 2$$

$$r = r_1r_2 = \vec{x}R_1\vec{u}\vec{x}R_2\vec{u} = \vec{x}(\vec{v}_1 + \vec{w}_1x^\sigma)\vec{x}R_2\vec{u}$$

$$R_x := (\vec{v}_1 + \vec{w}_1x^\sigma)\vec{x} = \left(\vec{v}_i x^{j_l} + \vec{w}_i x^{j_l + \sigma} \right)_{i,j}$$

$$\vec{r}_x := \vec{x}R_x = \left(\sum_0^N v_{1;i} x^{(i+j)l} + w_{1;i} x^{(i+j)l + \sigma} \right)_j$$

$$\vec{r}_s := R_2\vec{u} = \vec{v}_2 + \vec{w}_2x^\sigma$$

$$r = \vec{r}_x\vec{r}_s = \sum_0^N \sum_0^N (v_{1;i} x^{(i+j)l} + w_{1;i} x^{(i+j)l + \sigma})(v_{2;j} + w_{2;j}x^\sigma) =$$

$$= \sum_0^N \sum_0^N (v_{1;i}v_{2;j} + w_{1;i}w_{2;j})x \begin{bmatrix} i+j \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + (w_{1;i}v_{2;j} + v_{1;i}w_{2;j})x \begin{bmatrix} i+j \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Defining

$$R := \left(\alpha_k, \beta_k \right)_k \text{ matrix } (N + 1) \times 2; \quad N = n + m$$

with

$$\alpha_k = \sum_{i+j=k} v_{1;i}v_{2;j} + w_{1;i}w_{2;j} = \sum_0^k v_{1;i}v_{2;k-i} + w_{1;i}w_{2;k-i} = (\vec{v}_1 * \vec{v}_2)_k + (\vec{w}_1 * \vec{w}_2)_k$$

$$\beta_k = \sum_{i+j=k} w_{1;i}v_{2;j} + v_{1;i}w_{2;j} = \sum_0^k w_{1;i}v_{2;k-i} + v_{1;i}w_{2;k-i} = (\vec{v}_1 * \vec{w}_2)_k + (\vec{w}_1 * \vec{v}_2)_k$$

in order to have

$$r = \vec{x}R\vec{u}$$

moreover

$$R = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} \vec{v}_1 * \vec{v}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{w}_2 & \vec{v}_1 * \vec{w}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{v}_2 \\ \hline \vec{v}_1 * \vec{w}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{v}_2 & \vec{v}_1 * \vec{v}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{w}_2 \end{array} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} [R_1 * R_2]_{i,j} &= \sum_0^N \sum_0^1 R_{1;n,m} R_{2;i-n,j-m} = \sum_0^N R_{1;n,0} R_{2;i-n,j} + R_{1;n,1} R_{2;i-n,j-1} = \\ &= \sum_0^N v_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,j} + w_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,j-1} = \sum_0^N v_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,j} + w_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,j \oplus 1} \end{aligned}$$

where the last passage is possible only because the column indices are in \mathbb{F}_2 ; this implies the convolution is circular along columns [OSB99].

Since

$$\begin{aligned} [R_1 * R_2]_{i,0} &= \sum_0^N v_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,0} + w_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,1} = \sum_0^N v_{1;n} v_{2;i-n} + w_{1;n} w_{2;i-n} = (\vec{v}_1 * \vec{v}_2)_i + (\vec{w}_1 * \vec{w}_2)_i \\ [R_1 * R_2]_{i,1} &= \sum_0^N v_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,1} + w_{1;n} R_{2;i-n,0} = \sum_0^N v_{1;n} w_{2;i-n} + w_{1;n} v_{2;i-n} = (\vec{v}_1 * \vec{w}_2)_i + (\vec{w}_1 * \vec{v}_2)_i \end{aligned}$$

we can conclude that

$$R = R_1 * R_2$$

□

Remark 2.7.

$$\deg(r) \leq N = n + m = \deg(r_1) + \deg(r_2)$$

Lemma 2.11 (DFT of R). *Given $R = \begin{pmatrix} | & | \\ \vec{v} & \vec{w} \\ | & | \end{pmatrix}$ and $\hat{v} = \mathcal{F}[\vec{v}]$, $\hat{w} = \mathcal{F}[\vec{w}]$*

the discrete Fourier transform of R is

$$\hat{R} = \mathcal{F}[R] = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} \hat{v} + \hat{w} & \hat{v} - \hat{w} \\ \hline \hat{v} & \hat{w} \end{array} \right)$$

Proof. The two-dimensional Fourier transform could be done applying the usual Fourier transform on columns and then on rows [Sun18]:

$$R = \left(\begin{array}{c|c} | & | \\ \vec{v} & \vec{w} \\ | & | \end{array} \right) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}_{\text{col}}} \left(\begin{array}{c|c} | & | \\ \hat{v} & \hat{w} \\ | & | \end{array} \right) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}_{\text{row}}} \left(\begin{array}{c|c} \hat{v} + \hat{w} & \hat{v} - \hat{w} \\ \hline \hat{v} & \hat{w} \end{array} \right)$$

□

Theorem 2.9 (Perenomial product DFT).

$$R_1 * R_2 \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}} \hat{R}_1 \circ \hat{R}_2$$

Where \circ is the Hadamard product, which is multiply the two matrices element-wise.

Proof. From Lemma 2.11 we know that $\hat{R}_1 = \mathcal{F}[R_1] = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{v}_1 + \hat{w}_1 & \hat{v}_1 - \hat{w}_1 \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix}$

and $\hat{R}_2 = \mathcal{F}[R_2] = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{v}_2 + \hat{w}_2 & \hat{v}_2 - \hat{w}_2 \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix}$, so

$$R_1 \circ R_2 = \begin{pmatrix} (\hat{v}_1 + \hat{w}_1) \circ (\hat{v}_2 + \hat{w}_2) & (\hat{v}_1 - \hat{w}_1) \circ (\hat{v}_2 - \hat{w}_2) \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix} =: \begin{pmatrix} \hat{a} & \hat{b} \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix}$$

with

$$\hat{a} = \hat{v}_1 \circ \hat{v}_2 + \hat{v}_1 \circ \hat{w}_2 + \hat{w}_1 \circ \hat{v}_2 + \hat{w}_1 \circ \hat{w}_2$$

$$\hat{b} = \hat{v}_1 \circ \hat{v}_2 - \hat{v}_1 \circ \hat{w}_2 - \hat{w}_1 \circ \hat{v}_2 + \hat{w}_1 \circ \hat{w}_2$$

and

$$\hat{a} + \hat{b} = 2(\hat{v}_1 \circ \hat{v}_2 + \hat{w}_1 \circ \hat{w}_2) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}^{-1}} 2(\vec{v}_1 * \vec{v}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{w}_2); \quad \hat{a} + \hat{b} \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}^{-1}} a + b$$

$$\hat{a} - \hat{b} = 2(\hat{v}_1 \circ \hat{w}_2 + \hat{w}_1 \circ \hat{v}_2) \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}^{-1}} 2(\vec{v}_1 * \vec{w}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{v}_2); \quad \hat{a} - \hat{b} \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}^{-1}} a - b$$

finally

$$\begin{aligned} R_1 \circ R_2 &= \begin{pmatrix} \hat{a} & \hat{b} \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}_{\text{col}}^{-1}} \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix} \xrightarrow{\mathcal{F}_{\text{row}}^{-1}} \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} a + b & a - b \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \vec{v}_1 * \vec{v}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{w}_2 & \vec{v}_1 * \vec{w}_2 + \vec{w}_1 * \vec{v}_2 \\ | & | \\ | & | \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

□

2.3 Binomial theorem

Lemma 2.12 (Binomial expansion for dis-integer powers).

Given $\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_D$; $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$

$$(a+b)^{\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix}} = (a+b)^\sigma (a+b)^v = (a+b)^\sigma \sum_0^v \binom{v}{k} a^{v-k} b^k$$

Proof.

$$\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{Z}_D \Leftrightarrow p = \text{par} \left(\begin{bmatrix} v \\ p \end{bmatrix} \right) = 1 \oplus \text{par}(v)$$

$$(a+b)^\sigma (a+b)^v = (a+b)^{\sigma+v} = (a+b)^{\begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} v \\ \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix}} = (a+b)^{\begin{bmatrix} v \\ 1 \oplus \text{par}(v) \end{bmatrix}}$$

□

Theorem 2.10. *There is no perenomial expansion of $(a+b)^\sigma$ useful for Lemma 2.12.*

Proof. Suppose by contradiction there exists a perenomial equal to $(a+b)^\sigma$, so there would be a perenomial equal to $r(x) = (1+x)^\sigma$.

$$r(x) = (1+x)^\sigma = \begin{cases} 1 & x > -1 \\ -1 & x < -1 \end{cases}$$

$$r(x) = p(x) + q(x); \quad p \in P, q \in P_D$$

and since $\exists s \in P: q(x) = x^\sigma s(x)$

$$r(x) = p(x) + x^\sigma s(x)$$

So (being p and s polynomials and thus continuous), the only discontinuity point could be found in $x = 0$. But $(1+x)^\sigma$ is discontinuous in $x = -1$.

We can conclude that cannot exist a perenomial which represents $(1+x)^\sigma$ and so let alone for $(a+b)^\sigma$. □

Theorem 2.11. *For every function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which is zero only in a finite set of isolated points we can simplify*

$$(f(x))^\sigma = s \prod_1^n (x - z_i)^\sigma$$

with

$$s = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \text{sgn}(f(x))$$

$$\{z_1, \dots, z_n\} = \{z \in \mathbb{R} : f(z) = 0 \wedge \text{sgn}(f(z - \varepsilon)) \neq \text{sgn}(f(z + \varepsilon))\}$$

Proof. Every $(x - z_i)^\sigma$ in the product introduces a change of sign in z_i , as it is in $f(x)$.

Another way to see this is that $\prod_1^n (x - z_i)$ is a polynomial which zeros are $\{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$, all with multiplicity one. So the polynomial changes sign in the same points of $f(x)$. Then $\left(\prod_1^n (x - z_i)\right)^\sigma = \prod_1^n (x - z_i)^\sigma$.

Finally we have to adjust the initial sign, and since $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} (x - z_i)^\sigma = 1$ then $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} s \prod_1^n (x - z_i)^\sigma = s$. To have $\text{sgn}(f(x)) = s \prod_1^n (x - z_i)^\sigma$ we now must put $s = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \text{sgn}(f(x))$. \square

Lemma 2.13 (Perenomial transformations).

Horizontal translation *this is not possible:*

$$r(x - k) = p(x - k) + s(x - k)(x - k)^\sigma$$

but for Theorem 2.10 this is not a perenomial. For more informatons see Lemma 2.15.

Vertical translation $r(x) + k$ *is a perenomial:*

$$r(x) + k = (p(x) + k) + q(x)$$

Reflection $r(-x)$ *is a perenomial:*

$$r(-x) = p(-x) + s(-x)(-x)^\sigma = p(-x) - s(-x)(x)^\sigma$$

Horizontal stretch or shrink $r(kx)$ *is a perenomial:*

$$r(kx) = p(kx) + s(kx)(kx)^\sigma = p(kx) + (\text{sgn}(k)s(kx))(x)^\sigma$$

Vertical stretch or shrink $k \cdot r(x)$ *is a perenomial:*

$$k \cdot r(x) = k \cdot p(x) + k \cdot s(x)(x)^\sigma$$

2.4 Interpolation

Lemma 2.14 (Lagrange polynomial). *Given $n+1$ distinct points (x_i, y_i) we can always build a polynomial of minimal degree not greater than n , which passes trough all points, with the following formula [Dav75]:*

$$p(x) = \sum_0^n y_i \prod_0^n \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} \quad (2.5)$$

Theorem 2.12 (Lagrange dis-polynomial). *Given $n + 1$ distinct points (x_i, y_i) we can always build a dis-polynomial of minimal degree not greater than n , which passes through all points, with the following formula:*

$$q(x) = \sum_0^n y_i x_i^\sigma \prod_0^n_{j \neq i} \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} x^\sigma \quad (2.6)$$

Proof. If $q(x)$ is a dis-polynomial then $p(x) = q(x)x^\sigma$ is a polynomial and so we can apply Lemma 2.14 to find p and then obtain $q(x) = p(x)x^\sigma$

First of all obtain the points of p from those of q : $(x_i, y_i) \mapsto (x_i, y_i x_i^\sigma) = (x_i, y'_i)$

Then find p with Equation 2.5:

$$p(x) = \sum_0^n y'_i \prod_0^n_{j \neq i} \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} = \sum_0^n y_i x_i^\sigma \prod_0^n_{j \neq i} \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j}$$

Finally obtain $q(x) = p(x)x^\sigma$:

$$q(x) = p(x)x^\sigma = \sum_0^n y_i x_i^\sigma \prod_0^n_{j \neq i} \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} x^\sigma$$

□

Theorem 2.13 (Perenomial interpolation). *Given distinct (x_i, y_i) with $|\{i: x_i \leq 0\}| = |\{i: x_i \geq 0\}| = n + 1$ ¹ we can always build a perenomial of minimal degree not greater than n , which passes through all points, with the following algorithm:*

1. Interpolate the polynomial $a(x)$ with $(x_i, y_i): x_i \geq 0$
2. Interpolate the polynomial $c(x)$ with $(x_i, y_i): x_i \leq 0$
3. Obtain $r(x) = p(x) + q(x)x^\sigma$ with $p = \frac{a+c}{2}$ and $q = \frac{a-c}{2}$

Proof. Begin proving the theorem for $x \neq 0$:

$$r(x) = p(x) + q(x)x^\sigma = p(x) + q(x) =: a(x) \quad \forall x > 0$$

$$r(x) = p(x) + q(x)x^\sigma = p(x) - q(x) =: c(x) \quad \forall x < 0$$

So a and c are two polynomials of degree n which can be interpolated with $n + 1$ points (Lemma 2.14).

¹Namely $n + 1$ points with negative x and $n + 1$ points with positive x or n points with negative x , one point with $x = 0$ and n points with positive x .

Then we can obtain p and q with:

$$p = \frac{a+c}{2} = \frac{(p+q) + (p-q)}{2} = \frac{2p}{2} = p$$

$$q = \frac{a-c}{2} = \frac{(p+q) - (p-q)}{2} = \frac{2q}{2} = q$$

Finally $r(0) = p_0 + q_0 0^e$ is defined if and only if $q_0 = 0$ and so $q(0) = 0$ and thus $a(0) = c(0)$. For this a point $(0, r(0))$ could be used to interpolate both a and c . \square

Example 2.1. Begin interpolating a polynomial: $r(x) = x^2$. It is of grade two so we need 3 points with non-negative and 3 points with non-positive x :

i	x_i	y_i
0	-5	25
1	-2	4
2	0	0
3	3	9
4	5	25

Now let's interpolate $a(x)$:

$$a(x) = \sum_2^4 y_i \prod_2^4 \frac{x-x_j}{x_i-x_j} = 0 + \cancel{3} \frac{x(x-5)}{\cancel{3}(3-5)} + \cancel{25} \frac{x(x-3)}{\cancel{5}(5-3)} =$$

$$= x \frac{-3x + \cancel{3} \cdot 5 + 5x - \cancel{5} \cdot 3}{5-3} = x^2 \frac{5-3}{5-3} = x^2$$

Now let's interpolate $c(x)$:

$$c(x) = \sum_0^2 y_i \prod_0^2 \frac{x-x_j}{x_i-x_j} = \cancel{25} \frac{(x+2)x}{(-5+2)(-\cancel{5})} + \cancel{4} \frac{(x+5)x}{(-2+5)(-\cancel{2})} + 0 =$$

$$= x \frac{5x + \cancel{5} \cdot 2 - 2x - \cancel{2} \cdot 5}{5-2} = x^2 \frac{5-2}{5-2} = x^2$$

Then $p(x) = \frac{a(x)+c(x)}{2} = \frac{x^2}{2} = x^2$ and $q(x) = \frac{a(x)-c(x)}{2} = 0$, so $r(x) = p(x) + q(x)x^e = p(x) = x^2$.

Example 2.2. Now let's find a perenomial which interpolates the following points:

i	x_i	y_i
0	-5	5
1	-2	2
2	2	0
3	3	1

Begin interpolating $a(x)$:

$$a(x) = \sum_2^3 y_i \prod_{j \neq i}^3 \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} = 0 + 1 \frac{x - 2}{3 - 2} = x - 2$$

Then interpolate $c(x)$:

$$\begin{aligned} c(x) &= \sum_0^1 iy_i \prod_{j \neq i}^1 \frac{x - x_j}{x_i - x_j} = 5 \frac{x + 2}{-5 + 2} + 2 \frac{x + 5}{-2 + 5} = \\ &= \frac{-5x - 5 \cdot 2 + 2x + 2 \cdot 5}{5 - 2} = \frac{-3x}{3} = -x \end{aligned}$$

Now $p(x) = \frac{a(x)+c(x)}{2} = -1$ and $q(x) = \frac{a(x)-c(x)}{2} = \frac{-2x-2}{2} = x - 1$, finally $r(x) = p(x) + q(x)x^\sigma = -1 - x^\sigma + x^1$ which degree is one.

We can find a polynomial of degree 3 which interpolates the same points (see \tilde{p} in Figure 2.1), but it's clear that we cannot find a polynomial of degree 1 which interpolates them (the best linear approximation \tilde{p}' can be seen in the same figure).

2.5 Hyper-perenomials

Definition 2.10 (Hyper-perenomial). An hyper-perenomial $h(x)$ has the form:

$$h(x) = p_0(x) + \sum_1^n p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\sigma$$

where each $p_i(x)$ is a polynomial and each z_i a constant number.

Remark 2.8. We can write $h(x) = \sum_0^n p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\sigma$ with $z_0 \rightarrow -\infty$.

Remark 2.9. We can see that an hyper-perenomial is the sum of a perenomial and shifted (horizontal translated) dis-polynomials:

$$\begin{aligned} h(x) &= p_0(x) + \sum_1^n p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\sigma = p_0(x) + p_j(x)x^\sigma + \sum_1^n p_{i \neq j}(x)(x - z_i)^\sigma = \\ &= r(x) + \sum_1^n q_i(x - z_i) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.1: $r(x) = x^l - 1 - x^o$; $\tilde{p}(x) = \frac{1}{35}x^3 + \frac{3}{14}x^2 - \frac{43}{70}x + \frac{1}{7}$; $\tilde{p}'(x) = -\frac{22}{41}x + \frac{71}{41}$

because $p_i(x) = s_i(x - z_i)$ and so $s_i(x - z_i)(x - z_i)^\sigma = q_i(x - z_i)$.

Also a sum of shifted perenomials is an hyper-perenomial:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_1^n r_i(x - z_i) &= \sum_1^n s_i(x - z_i) + t_i(z - z_i)(x - z_i)^\sigma = \\ &= \sum_1^n s_i(x - z_i) + \sum_1^n t_i(z - z_i)(x - z_i)^\sigma = \\ &= p_0(x) + \sum_1^n p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\sigma \end{aligned}$$

with $p_0(x) = \sum_1^n s_i(x - z_i)$ and $p_i(x) = t_i(x - z_i)$ polynomials.

Lemma 2.15 (Hyper-perenomial transformations).

Horizontal translation $h(x - k)$ is an hyper-perenomial:

$$h(x - k) = p_0(x - k) + \sum_1^n p_i(x - k)(x - z_i - k)^\sigma$$

Vertical translation $h(x) + k$ is an hyper-perenomial:

$$h(x) + k = (p_0(x) + k) + \sum_1^n p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\sigma$$

Reflection $h(-x)$ is an hyper-perenomial:

$$h(-x) = p_0(-x) + \sum_1^n p_i(-x)(-x - z_i)^\sigma = p_0(-x) - \sum_1^n p_i(-x)(x + z_i)^\sigma$$

Horizontal stretch or shrink $h(kx)$ is an hyper-perenomial:

$$h(kx) = p_0(kx) + \sum_1^n p_i(kx)(kx - z_i)^\sigma$$

and

$$(kx - z_i)^\sigma = (k(x - z_i/k))^\sigma = \text{sgn}(k)(x - z_i/k)^\sigma$$

Vertical stretch or shrink $k \cdot h(x)$ is an hyper-perenomial:

$$k \cdot h(x) = k \cdot p_0(x) + \sum_1^n k \cdot p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\sigma$$

Theorem 2.14 (Sum of hyper-perenomials). *Given $h_1(x) = p_{1,0}(x) + \sum_1^n p_{1,i}(x)(x - z_{1,i})^\sigma$ and $h_2(x) = p_{2,0}(x) + \sum_1^m p_{2,j}(x)(x - z_{2,j})^\sigma$, then $h_1(x) + h_2(x)$ is an hyper-perenomial.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} h(x) &= h_1(x) + h_2(x) = \\ &= p_{1,0}(x) + \sum_1^n p_{1,i}(x)(x - z_{1,i})^\sigma + p_{2,0}(x) + \sum_1^m p_{2,j}(x)(x - z_{2,j})^\sigma = \\ &= (p_{1,i}(x) + p_{2,0}(x)) + \sum_1^n p_{1,i}(x)(x - z_{1,i})^\sigma + \sum_1^m p_{2,j}(x)(x - z_{2,j})^\sigma = \\ &= p_0(x) + \sum_1^c p_k(x)(x - z_k)^\sigma \end{aligned}$$

with $p_0(x) = p_{1,i}(x) + p_{2,0}(x)$ and

1. $\forall z_{1,i} = z_{2,j} \exists z_k = z_{1,i} = z_{2,j} : p_k = p_{1,i} + p_{2,j}$
2. $\forall z_{1,i} : \nexists z_{2,j} = z_{1,i} \exists z_k = z_{1,i} : p_k = p_{1,i}$
3. $\forall z_{2,j} : \nexists z_{1,i} = z_j \exists z_k = z_{2,j} : p_k = p_{2,j}$

Thus $c = |\{z_k \forall k\}| = |\{z_{1,i}, z_{2,j} \forall i, j\}| \leq n + m$. □

Lemma 2.16.

$$(x - a)^\alpha (x - b)^\alpha = 1 - (x - x_1)^\alpha + (x - x_2)^\alpha$$

with $x_{1,2} = a, b$ and $x_1 < x_2$.

The result is an hyper-perenomial.

Proof.

$$(x - a)^\alpha (x - b)^\alpha = ((x - a)(x - b))^\alpha = (x^2 - (a + b)x + ab)^\alpha$$

which is the sign of a U-shaped parabola, so equal to 1 if it does not intersect the x axis (or intersects it only in the vertex); otherwise it is always 1, except between the two points of intersection with the x axis where the sign value is -1.

So with $\Delta = (a + b)^2 - 4ab = (a - b)^2$ the points of intersection are $x_{1,2} = \frac{a+b \pm \sqrt{\Delta}}{2} = a, b$.

We can then see that the hyper-perenomial $1 - (x - x_1)^\alpha + (x - x_2)^\alpha$ with $x_1 < x_2$ is the result we wanted, when the parabola intersects the x axis. This is valid also in the case of $\Delta = 0$, being $a = b$ and so $x_1 = x_2$. Since the delta can never be negative, we do not need to cover the case where the parabola does not intersect the x axis. \square

Lemma 2.17 (Product between polynomial and hyper-perenomial). *The product between a polynomial and an hyper-perenomial is an hyper-perenomial.*

Proof.

$$p(x)h(x) = p(x) \left(\sum_0^n p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\alpha \right) = \sum_0^n p(x)p_i(x)(x - z_i)^\alpha$$

\square

Theorem 2.15 (Product between hyper-perenomials). *The product of two (or more) hyper-perenomials is an hyper-perenomial.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
p_1(x) &= \sum_0^n p_{1,i}(x)(x - z_{1,i})^\sigma; & p_2(x) &= \sum_0^m p_{2,j}(x)(x - z_{2,j})^\sigma \\
p(x) &= p_1(x)p_2(x) = \sum_0^n p_{1,i}(x)(x - z_{1,i})^\sigma \sum_0^m p_{2,j}(x)(x - z_{2,j})^\sigma = \\
&= \sum_0^n \sum_0^m p_{1,i}(x)(x - z_{1,i})^\sigma p_{2,j}(x)(x - z_{2,j})^\sigma = \\
&= \sum_0^n \sum_0^m p_{1,i}(x)p_{2,j}(x)(x - z_{1,i})^\sigma (x - z_{2,j})^\sigma = \\
&= \sum_0^n \sum_0^m p_{i,j}(x)h_{i,j}(x)
\end{aligned}$$

where $p_{i,j} = p_{1,i}p_{2,j}$ is a polynomial and $h_{i,j}(x) = (x - z_{1,i})^\sigma (x - z_{2,j})^\sigma$ an hyper-perenomial, for Lemma 2.16. Then for Lemma 2.17 $p_{i,j}(x)h_{i,j}(x)$ is an hyper-perenomial and for Theorem 2.14 the sum is itself an hyper-perenomial. \square

Chapter 3

Selector function

3.1 Sign function

$$\text{sgn}(x) := x^{\circ}$$

$$y = \text{sgn}(x)$$

As we can see, this function (which is the odd unit of perenomials, as already seen in chapter 2) returns the sign of its argument.

Remark 3.1. Sign is an odd function, in fact all the exponents (\circ) of its perenomial form are odd, and so it is an odd-nomial.

3.2 Heaviside step function

$$\mathbf{1}(x) := \begin{cases} 0 & : x < 0 \\ 1 & : x > 0 \end{cases}$$

$$y = \mathbb{1}(x)$$

As we can see this function returns 1 for positive numbers, 0 for negative ones and it is not defined in zero.

Theorem 3.1 (Perenomial form of the unit step function).

$$\mathbb{1}(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}x^\sigma$$

Proof. Each function can be written as the sum of its even part and its odd part:

$$\mathbb{1}_e(x) := \frac{\mathbb{1}(x) + \mathbb{1}(-x)}{2} = \frac{1}{2}$$

because $\mathbb{1}(x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x < 0 \Leftrightarrow -x > 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathbb{1}(-x) = 1$;

$\mathbb{1}(x) = 1 \Leftrightarrow x > 0 \Leftrightarrow -x < 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathbb{1}(-x) = 0$;

so $\mathbb{1}(x) + \mathbb{1}(-x) = 1$.

$$\mathbb{1}_o(x) := \frac{\mathbb{1}(x) - \mathbb{1}(-x)}{2} = \frac{\text{sgn}(x)}{2} = \frac{x^\sigma}{2}$$

because $\mathbb{1}(x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x < 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathbb{1}(-x) = 1$; $x < 0 \Rightarrow \mathbb{1}(x) - \mathbb{1}(-x) = -1$

$\mathbb{1}(x) = 1 \Leftrightarrow x > 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathbb{1}(-x) = 0$; $x > 0 \Rightarrow \mathbb{1}(x) - \mathbb{1}(-x) = +1$

$$\mathbb{1}(x) = \mathbb{1}_e(x) + \mathbb{1}_o(x) = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}x^\sigma$$

□

Remark 3.2. The function $\mathbb{1}$ is neither even nor odd, in fact its perenomial form $(\frac{1}{2}x^0 + \frac{1}{2}x^\sigma)$ contains both even exponents (0) and odd ones (σ), so its neither a even- nor an odd-nomial.

Lemma 3.1 (Unit step function with opposite argument).

$$\mathbb{1}(-x) = 1 - \mathbb{1}(x)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbb{1}(-x) &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-x)^\alpha}{2} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-1)^\alpha x^\alpha}{2} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(-1)x^\alpha}{2} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{x^\alpha}{2} = \\ &= -\left(-\frac{1}{2} + \frac{x^\alpha}{2}\right) = -\left(\frac{1}{2} - 1 + \frac{x^\alpha}{2}\right) = 1 - \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{x^\alpha}{2}\right) = 1 - \mathbb{1}(x)\end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 3.2.

$$\mathbb{1}(\alpha f(x)) = \mathbb{1}(\operatorname{sgn}(\alpha)f(x)) \quad \forall \alpha \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}\alpha &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \cdot 0 \\ 1 \cdot 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \alpha \cdot \alpha \Rightarrow \alpha^\alpha = (\alpha^\alpha)^\alpha \\ \mathbb{1}(\alpha f(x)) &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(\alpha f(x))^\alpha}{2} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{\alpha^\alpha f^\alpha(x)}{2} = \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(\alpha^\alpha)^\alpha f^\alpha(x)}{2} = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} + \frac{(\alpha^\alpha f(x))^\alpha}{2} = \mathbb{1}(\alpha^\alpha f(x)) = \mathbb{1}(\operatorname{sgn}(\alpha)f(x))\end{aligned}$$

□

3.3 Rect function

$$\Pi(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & : |x| \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & : \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$y = \Pi(x)$$

3.4 Selector function

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & : x \in [a, b] \\ 0 & : \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{with } a, b \in \mathbb{R}$$

$$y = \mathfrak{z}_a^b(x)$$

Remark 3.3.

$$\mathbf{1}(x) = \lim_{b \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{z}_0^b$$

Being the unit step a particular case of the selector function, all the following lemmas and theorems for the selector function are valid also for the unit step one.

Lemma 3.3 (Selector function as rect).

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x) = \Pi\left(\frac{x - \mu}{\Delta}\right) \quad \text{with } \mu = \frac{a + b}{2}; \Delta = |a - b|$$

Proof.

$$\Pi\left(\frac{x - \mu}{\Delta}\right) := \begin{cases} 1 & : \left|\frac{x - \mu}{\Delta}\right| \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 & : \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = \begin{cases} 1 & : x \in [a, b] \\ 0 & : \text{otherwise} \end{cases} =: \mathfrak{z}_a^b$$

because:

$$\begin{aligned} \left|\frac{x - \mu}{\Delta}\right| \leq \frac{1}{2} &\Leftrightarrow 2|x - \mu| \leq |\Delta| = \Delta \Leftrightarrow 2(x - \mu) \in [-\Delta, \Delta] \Leftrightarrow \\ &\Leftrightarrow -\Delta \leq 2x - 2\mu \leq \Delta \Leftrightarrow \frac{2\mu - \Delta}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{2\mu + \Delta}{2} \end{aligned}$$

We can assume $b \geq a$ (without loss of generality since a and b are used only in commutative operations: sum and difference in absolute value) and so $\Delta = |a - b| = b - a$

$$\frac{2\mu - \Delta}{2} = \frac{(a + b) - (b - a)}{2} = \frac{2a}{2} = a$$

$$\frac{2\mu + \Delta}{2} = \frac{(a + b) + (b - a)}{2} = \frac{2b}{2} = b$$

$$\frac{2\mu - \Delta}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{2\mu + \Delta}{2} \Leftrightarrow a \leq x \leq b \Leftrightarrow x \in [a, b]$$

□

Remark 3.4.

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x) = \Pi \left(\frac{x - \frac{a+b}{2}}{|a-b|} \right) = \Pi \left(\frac{x - \frac{b+a}{2}}{|b-a|} \right) = \mathfrak{z}_b^a(x)$$

Therefore all lemmas and theorems valid for $a < b$ are valid for $a > b$ too.

Lemma 3.4 (Selector function translation).

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x - c) = \mathfrak{z}_{a+c}^{b+c}(x)$$

Proof.

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x - c) = \Pi \left(\frac{(x - c) - \frac{a+b}{2}}{|a-b|} \right) = \Pi \left(\frac{x - c - \frac{a+b}{2}}{|a-b|} \right)$$

$$-c - \frac{a+b}{2} = -\frac{a+b+2c}{2} = -\frac{(a+c) + (b+c)}{2}$$

$$|a-b| = |(a+c) - (b+c)|$$

$$\Pi \left(\frac{x - c - \frac{a+b}{2}}{|a-b|} \right) = \Pi \left(\frac{x - \frac{(a+c)+(b+c)}{2}}{|(a+c) - (b+c)|} \right) = \mathfrak{z}_{a+c}^{b+c}(x)$$

□

Lemma 3.5 (Selector function with opposite argument).

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(-x) = \mathfrak{z}_{-a}^{-b}(x)$$

Proof.

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(-x) = \Pi\left(\frac{-x - \frac{a+b}{2}}{|a-b|}\right) = \Pi\left(-\frac{x + \frac{a+b}{2}}{|-(a-b)|}\right) = \Pi\left(-\frac{x - \frac{(-a)+(-b)}{2}}{|(-a) - (-b)|}\right) =$$

Being rect even

$$= \Pi\left(\frac{x - \frac{(-a)+(-b)}{2}}{|(-a) - (-b)|}\right) = \mathfrak{z}_{-a}^{-b}(x)$$

□

Lemma 3.6.

$$\Pi(x) = \mathfrak{z}_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{+\frac{1}{2}}(x)$$

Proof.

$$\mu = \frac{\left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)}{2} = 0; \Delta = \left| \left(-\frac{1}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \right| = |-1| = 1$$

$$\mathfrak{z}_{-\frac{1}{2}}^{+\frac{1}{2}}(x) = \Pi\left(\frac{x - \mu}{\Delta}\right) = \Pi\left(\frac{x - 0}{1}\right) = \Pi(x)$$

□

Remark 3.5. Being rect a particular case of the selector function, all the following lemmas and theorems for the selector function are valid also for the rect one.

3.5 Indicator function

$$\chi_A(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & : x \in A \\ 0 & : \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Remark 3.6.

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x) := \begin{cases} 1 & : x \in [a, b] \\ 0 & : \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = \chi_{[a,b]}$$

Being the selector function a particular case of the indicator function, all the following lemmas and theorems for the indicator function are valid also for the selector one.

Lemma 3.7 (Indicator of the intersection).

$$\chi_{A \cap B} = \chi_A \chi_B$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_A \chi_B &= \begin{cases} 0 \cdot 0 = 0 & : x \notin A \wedge x \notin B \Leftrightarrow x \notin A \cap B \\ 1 \cdot 0 = 0 & : x \in A \wedge x \notin B \Rightarrow x \notin A \cap B \\ 0 \cdot 1 = 0 & : x \notin A \wedge x \in B \Rightarrow x \notin A \cap B \\ 1 \cdot 1 = 1 & : x \in A \wedge x \in B \Leftrightarrow x \in A \cap B \end{cases} = \\ &= \begin{cases} 0 & : x \notin A \cap B \\ 1 & : x \in A \cap B \end{cases} = \chi_{A \cap B} \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 3.8. *If $a < b$ then:*

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b = \mathbf{1}(x - a)\mathbf{1}(b - x)$$

Proof. Being $[a, b] = [a, \infty) \cap (-\infty, b]$, from Lemma 3.7 we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{z}_a^b(x) &= \mathfrak{z}_a^\infty(x)\mathfrak{z}_{-\infty}^b(x) \\ \mathfrak{z}_a^\infty(x) &= \mathfrak{z}_0^\infty(x - a) = \mathbf{1}(x - a) \\ \mathfrak{z}_{-\infty}^b(x) &= \mathfrak{z}_\infty^{-b}(-x) = \mathfrak{z}_{-b}^\infty(-x) = \mathfrak{z}_0^\infty(b - x) = \mathbf{1}(b - x) \\ \mathfrak{z}_a^b(x) &= \mathfrak{z}_a^\infty(x)\mathfrak{z}_{-\infty}^b(x) = \mathbf{1}(x - a)\mathbf{1}(b - x) \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 3.7. Thanks to this lemma we can easily calculate the autoconvolution of the unit step:

$$[\mathbf{1} * \mathbf{1}](x) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \mathbf{1}(\tau)\mathbf{1}(x - \tau)d\tau = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \mathfrak{z}_0^x(\tau)d\tau = x\mathbf{1}(x)$$

since it's the area of a rectangle with unitary height and width $\Delta = |0 - x| = x$.

Obviously the rectangle area (x) is multiplied by a unit step, because the lemma is valid only for $x > 0$. If $x \leq 0$ it's clear that the convolution would return 0 (in a coherent way with the multiplication by the step) since $x - \tau \leq \tau \quad \forall \tau$ and so the product between the two steps is always zero.

Lemma 3.9. *If $a < b$ then:*

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b = \mathbf{1}(x - a)[1 - \mathbf{1}(x - b)]$$

Proof.

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b = \mathbf{1}(x-a)\mathbf{1}(b-x) = \mathbf{1}(x-a)[1 - \mathbf{1}(-(b-x))] = \mathbf{1}(x-a)[1 - \mathbf{1}(x-b)]$$

□

Lemma 3.10. *If $a < b$ then:*

$$\mathbf{1}(x-a)\mathbf{1}(x-b) = \mathbf{1}(x-b)$$

Proof.

$$\mathbf{1}(x-a)\mathbf{1}(x-b) = \mathfrak{z}_a^\infty(x)\mathfrak{z}_b^\infty(x) = \mathfrak{z}_b^\infty(x) = \mathbf{1}(x-b)$$

because $[a, \infty) \cap [b, \infty) = [b, \infty)$

□

Lemma 3.11. *Se $a < b$ allora:*

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b = \mathbf{1}(x-a) - \mathbf{1}(x-b)$$

Proof.

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b = \mathbf{1}(x-a)[1 - \mathbf{1}(x-b)] = \mathbf{1}(x-a) - \mathbf{1}(x-a)\mathbf{1}(x-b) = \mathbf{1}(x-a) - \mathbf{1}(x-b)$$

□

Theorem 3.2 (Hyper-perenomial form of the selector function).

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b(x) = \frac{1}{2}(x-a)^\sigma - \frac{1}{2}(x-b)^\sigma$$

Proof.

$$\mathfrak{z}_a^b = \mathbf{1}(x-a) - \mathbf{1}(x-b) = \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}(x-a)^\sigma \right] - \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}(x-b)^\sigma \right]$$

□

3.6 Functions defined by cases with selector function

Theorem 3.3 (Functions defined by cases as a single formula). *Thanks to the selector function we can write each function defined by cases (undefined in the extremities of the cases for which the limit does not exist) as a single formula.*

Proof.

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} f_0(x) & x < a_0 \\ \vdots & \\ f_i(x) & a_i \leq x \leq b_i = f_0(x)\mathbb{1}(a_0-x) + \sum_1^{n-1} f_i(x)\mathbb{1}_{a_i}^{b_i}(x) + f_n(x)\mathbb{1}(x-b_n) \\ \vdots & \\ f_n(x) & x > b_n \end{cases}$$

□

Theorem 3.4 (Functions defined by cases as hyper-perenomials). *If the functions $f_i(x)$ of Theorem 3.3 are hyper-perenomials, then the resulting formula is an hyper-perenomial.*

Proof. $f_i(x)$ are hyper-perenomials by definition. There exists an hyper-perenomial expression both for $\mathbb{1}$ (Theorem 3.1) and $\mathbb{1}_{a_i}^{b_i}$ (Theorem 3.2), so for Theorem 2.15 the result is still an hyper-perenomial. □

Example 3.1.

$$g(x) = x + 4; \quad h(x) = 3; \quad i(x) = x$$

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} g(x) & x < -1 \\ h(x) & -1 \leq x \leq 3 \\ i(x) & x > 3 \end{cases}$$

$$y = f(x)$$

$$y = \mathfrak{t}_{-\infty}^{-1}(x) = \mathbf{1}(-x - 1) \quad y = \mathfrak{t}_{-1}^3(x) \quad y = \mathfrak{t}_3^{\infty}(x) = \mathbf{1}(x - 3)$$

So the function $f(x)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \mathbf{1}(-x - 1) \cdot g(x) + \mathfrak{t}_{-1}^3(x) \cdot h(x) + \mathbf{1}(x - 3) \cdot i(x) = \\ &= (x + 4)[1 - \mathbf{1}(x + 1)] + 3[\mathbf{1}(x + 1) - \mathbf{1}(x - 3)] + x\mathbf{1}(x - 3) = \\ &= x + 4 + (3 - x - 4)\mathbf{1}(x + 1) + (x - 3)\mathbf{1}(x - 3) = \\ &= x + 4 - (1 + x)\mathbf{1}(x + 1) + (x - 3)\mathbf{1}(x - 3) = \\ &= x + 4 - (1 + x) \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{(x + 1)^{\epsilon}}{2} \right] + (x - 3) \left[\frac{1}{2} + \frac{(x - 3)^{\epsilon}}{2} \right] = \\ &= x + 4 - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{x}{2} - \frac{(x + 1)^{\epsilon}}{2} + \frac{x}{2} - \frac{3}{2} + \frac{(x - 3)^{\epsilon}}{2} = \\ &= 2 + x - \frac{|x + 1|}{2} + \frac{|x - 3|}{2} \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3.8. As we can see the fact the selector function is undefined on the extremes doesn't matter: all the generated discontinuities are removable, and so in result we have a continue function as we wanted.

Example 3.2.

$$g(x) = e^x; \quad h(x) = x^2; \quad i(x) = x - 3$$

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} g(x) & x < -1 \\ h(x) & -1 < x < 2 \\ i(x) & x > 2 \end{cases}$$

$$y = f(x)$$

$$y = \mathfrak{t}_{-\infty}^{-1}(x) = \mathbf{1}(-x - 1) \quad y = \mathfrak{t}_{-1}^2(x) \quad y = \mathfrak{t}_2^{\infty}(x) = \mathbf{1}(x - 2)$$

So the function $f(x)$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x) &= \mathbf{1}(-x - 1) \cdot g(x) + \mathfrak{t}_{-1}^2(x) \cdot h(x) + \mathbf{1}(x - 2) \cdot i(x) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \{ [1 - (x + 1)^{\sigma}] e^x + [(x + 1)^{\sigma} - (x - 2)^{\sigma}] x^2 + [1 + (x - 2)^{\sigma}] (x - 3) \} = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} [e^x + (x + 1)^{\sigma} (x^2 - e^x) - (x - 2)^{\sigma} (x^2 - x + 3) + x - 3] \end{aligned}$$

Future work

In this chapter we will see some ideas for future works on this topic.

F.1 Applications

Obviously an important topic to explore are the possible real applications of the complete integers. In this document we saw them only for theoretical pleasure, but without any real application they are useless.

F.2 Parity extension

It could be useful to extend the parity concept to cover all \mathbb{Q}_C and not only \mathbb{Q}_H . Obviously two values will be not enough, so one idea could be to use the *parity measure* which states how much an integer is even, and then extend it to rationals:

$$\widetilde{\text{par}}(z) = 0 \quad \forall z \in \mathbb{Z}_o \tag{F.1}$$

$$\widetilde{\text{par}}(2) = 1 \tag{F.2}$$

$$\widetilde{\text{par}}(a \cdot b) = \widetilde{\text{par}}(a) + \widetilde{\text{par}}(b) \tag{F.3}$$

$$\widetilde{\text{par}}\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = \widetilde{\text{par}}(a) - \widetilde{\text{par}}(b) \tag{F.4}$$

This works in \mathbb{Q} , but not in \mathbb{Q}_C (e.g. $\widetilde{\text{par}}(l) = \widetilde{\text{par}}\left(\frac{2}{2}\right) = \widetilde{\text{par}}(2) - \widetilde{\text{par}}(2) = 0$ as for odd numbers). So another path must be followed.

F.3 Perenomial extension

We saw that perenomials extend polynomials but loosing the binomial expansion closure property (Theorem 2.10). It would be useful to extend perenomials in something closed under binomial expansion.

F.4 Complete integers and complex numbers

$$\ln(-1) = \ln(e^{\pi i}) = \pi i \Rightarrow i = \frac{\ln(-1)}{\pi} \quad (\text{F.5})$$

so

$$(e^{ai})^l = e^{ail} = e^{ial} = e^{ila} = e^{\frac{\ln(-1)}{\pi} la} = (-1)^{l \frac{a}{\pi}} = |-1|^{\frac{a}{\pi}} = 1^{\frac{a}{\pi}} = 1 \quad (\text{F.6})$$

but

$$(e^{ai})^l = e^{ail} \neq e^{ali} = e^{lai} = |e|^{ai} = e^{ai} = \cos(a) + i \sin(a) \quad (\text{F.7})$$

In Equation F.6 we commuted l only with real numbers ($al = la$ and $\frac{1}{\pi} la = l \frac{a}{\pi}$) and we get an expected result since $|e^{ai}| = 1$. Besides in Equation F.7 we tried to commute l with i but we get another result, so we can guess l and i cannot commute.

Another future work could be investigating how complete integers and complex numbers work together.

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